

Access to quiet green areas in European Urban Centres

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Summary

Urban quiet green spaces are essential for enhancing the quality of life in cities, offering benefits such as improved health, well-being, and positive environmental impacts. This report investigates the accessibility and distribution of these spaces within European urban centres, focusing on the impact of road traffic noise. The findings reveal that only 34% of the population in the 233 cities analysed can access quiet green areas within a 400-meter walk. This is significantly lower than the 65% accessibility to all green areas inside the cities without considering noise levels. There is considerable variation in accessibility between cities and countries. Northern European countries generally have higher accessibility rates, with Helsinki notably achieving 95% accessibility. In contrast, smaller countries like Cyprus, Belgium and Malta have much lower accessibility. The current study also demonstrates that while the share of the street network covered by noise contour bands does influence slightly the total percentage of quiet green areas in an urban centre, its overall impact on the results is relatively low, and the average differences are not significant.

The study highlights the importance of local factors, such as geographic context, population density, and urban planning, in determining accessibility. For example, cities with proactive green space policies and strong community involvement tend to have higher accessibility rates. Even if quiet green areas are available, their uneven distribution can lead to disparities in accessibility. Cities with a more homogeneous distribution of green spaces show higher accessibility than cities with green areas concentrated on the periphery. Preserving existing green spaces and their acoustic quality is crucial. Expanding green urban areas, especially in city centres, is challenging due to historical and geographic constraints. Urban planning should focus on increasing the number of quiet green spaces and ensuring these areas are evenly distributed and easily accessible. This includes implementing noise action plans and engaging communities in urban planning processes.

The methodology presented in this report provides a valuable tool for assessing the accessibility of quiet green areas in urban centres. While there are general trends, local factors play a significant role, and results should be interpreted cautiously. Effective urban planning and preservation strategies are essential for improving accessibility to these vital urban spaces.

1 Introduction

Urban quiet green spaces play a vital role in enhancing the quality of life for city dwellers. These areas provide numerous benefits, ranging from improved health and well-being to positive environmental and social impacts (Votsi et al., 2017).

As urbanisation continues to accelerate globally, policymakers and urban planners have increasingly recognised the importance of preserving and expanding green spaces within cities (Barboza et al., 2021).

The Environmental Noise Directive (END) acknowledges the necessity of protecting quiet areas inside urban agglomerations and in open country, leading member states to its definition and protection. Moreover, the EU's Zero Pollution Action Plan include, among the key targets for 2030, a 30% reduction in the proportion of people chronically affected by transport noise. According to EEA (EEA, 2019), road traffic noise is the most dominant source of environmental noise, with an estimated 113 million people affected by long-term daily average noise levels of at least 55 dB(A) in Europe. In addition to their relevance to health-related issues, and considering the scope and requirements of this analysis, noise contour maps from roads in agglomerations provide the most suitable information due to their extensive coverage across Europe.

Building on previous work conducted by the European Environment Agency (EEA) and the European Topic Centre (ETC) (Sainz de la Maza et al., 2022), this study aims to update and refine the methodology for assessing quiet green spaces in urban environments. The primary objectives of this research are threefold:

- Update the methodology to focus on urban centres as a more stable reference unit for analysis.
- Develop a comparable approach to the methodology established by the Directorate-General for Regional and Urban Policy (DG Regio), specifically addressing the definition of green urban areas and their accessibility within a 400-meter walking distance.
- Conduct a comprehensive analysis of the distribution and accessibility to quiet green areas in 233 European cities (Table A1.1 in Annex 1) by intersecting road noise contour maps with green areas within urban centres.

2 Methodology

2.1 Overview

The methodology applied in this analysis is based on spatial analysis combining road traffic noise with green urban areas, based on previous work (Eionet Report - ETC/ATNI 2021/4), as well as the accessibility approach developed by DG Regio (Poelman, 2018).

The methodology can be outlined as follows:

- Delineation of green urban areas. Copernicus Urban Atlas data already provides a class « green urban areas » defined as "public green areas for predominantly recreational use such as gardens, zoos, parks, castle parks; suburban natural areas that have become and are managed as urban parks". But especially at the fringe of cities, the distinction between "green urban areas" and forests is not easily made. For this reason, we also included the Urban Atlas class "forests" in the analysis. It should be noted that Urban Atlas provide the information at the resolution of a minimum mapping unit of 0,25 ha, capturing relatively small patches, so the green urban areas included in the analysis are those at least 0,25 ha.
- Identification of potential quiet green areas (GQA). An additional attribute is assigned to green urban areas defined in the previous step: the acoustic quality. Data reported by Member States under the Environmental Noise Directive is considered for that. One of the information

provided (not mandatory) is the noise contour bands from noise sources (in this case, road traffic). These noise bands have a minimum threshold of 55 dB L_{den}. In this analysis, we have labelled quiet areas as those below 55 dB L_{den} due to road traffic noise.

- Calculation of service areas (all streets within 400 m walk from the potential GQA). The service area is the area that can be reached on foot within 400 meters of a quiet green area, considering the street network.
- Intersection of service areas with polygons containing population as an attribute. Service areas defined in the previous step intersect with the polygons of Urban Atlas, which contain data on the population to determine the portion of the population that lives within walking distance of a quiet green area.
- Calculation of statistics and indicators

2.2 Selection of most relevant noise sources

This section presents the rationale for prioritizing road traffic noise maps to identify quiet areas within urban centres. Road traffic is identified as the main source of environmental noise.

Road traffic noise exposure affects a significantly larger population than rail, aircraft, and industrial noise sources. This pattern is consistently observed across European, national, and local levels, encompassing inside and outside urban areas (EEA, 2020).

Another important factor to consider is data availability. The prevalence of road transportation infrastructure has resulted in a substantially more extensive collection of road noise maps delivered by member states compared to those for railways, aircraft, and industrial noise sources inside cities. The availability of road noise maps compared with other noise sources enables a more comprehensive analysis of urban centres, providing a broader and more diverse dataset that enhances our understanding of quiet areas in European cities.

Additionally, in most urban centres, road and railway noise maps demonstrate significant spatial and infrastructural overlap, reflecting the integrated transportation networks of metropolitan areas.

A comparative analysis of road and rail noise maps in urban centres of selected cities where noise maps for roads and railways where available has been conducted. The results of the analysis can be found in Table 2.1, where the percentage of area overlap of noise maps from both noise sources is shown. Figure 2.1 illustrates the case of Vienna.

Table 2.1 Percentage of overlap of road and railway noise contour maps (≥ 55 dB L_{den})

Urban centre	Country	Percentage of area overlap in noise contour maps for roads and railways
Vienna	Austria	73.53
Brno	Checkia	59.03
Clermont-Ferrand	France	61.39
Oberhausen	Germany	91.86
Norrkoping	Sweden	79.81

Figure 2.1 Road and railway noise contour maps overlap in the agglomeration of Vienna

2.3 City delineation

The Environmental Noise Directive (END) refer to cities as "agglomerations"; its delineation is left to Member State criteria. These agglomerations are above 100,000 inhabitants and have a population density such that the Member State considers it an urbanised area.

To have more comparable delineations and stability (fewer changes over time), we adopted the urban centre delineation described by Eurostat (Eurostat, 2024). Moreover, adopting this delineation, the results are also comparable with the assessment done by DG Regio on accessibility to green urban areas (Poelman, 2018). However, urban centres have to be filled in with information coming from two other data sets with different delineations (Figure 2.2 and Table 2.2):

- Urban Atlas. Urban Atlas provides the "Green Urban Areas" and "Forest" classes to delineate green areas. The residential population in each built-up polygon of Urban Atlas is needed to estimate the percentage of the population having access to quiet green areas. Urban Atlas is based on the FUA and core city delineation (Table 2.2).
- Noise contour maps inside END agglomerations. Noise contour maps represent the noise level due to specific noise sources, such as road traffic noise. The data is provided in polygons representing ranges of 5 dB consecutive bands starting at the lower threshold set by the END (55 dB L_{den}). Noise contour maps are provided voluntarily by Member States in the case of agglomerations. Member States define the delineation of the agglomerations following the END specifications (Table 2.2).

Figure 2.2 Urban centre delineation (black), noise contour maps traffic noise inside agglomerations -including END agglomeration delineation (red), and green urban areas from Urban Atlas 2018 for Bordeaux (France)

Table 2.2 Description and comparison of different delineations of cities

Delineation	Description	Pros	Cons	Source
FUA, core city	<p>A city consists of one or more local units, with at least 50% of its population in an urban centre. A local unit can be either administrative or statistical. Examples of administrative units include a municipality, a district, a neighbourhood or metropolitan area. Some of these administrative units also play a political role as electoral districts or local government areas.</p> <p>A Functional Urban Area (FUA) consist of a densely inhabited city and a less densely populated commuting zone whose labour market is highly integrated with the city.</p>	Comparable delineation across Europe used as reference unit by several European institutions (Eurostat, EEA, Copernicus)	FUA and core city are less stable compared with the urban centre.	(Dijkstra et al., 2019)
Agglomeration	<p>"Agglomeration" shall mean part of a territory, delimited by the Member State, having a population in excess of 100,000 persons and a population density such that the Member State considers it to be an urbanised area</p> <p>Noise contour maps inside agglomerations for road traffic noise are provided at agglomeration level on voluntary basis, and include different coverage of streets and major roads.</p>	In accordance with the END, adapted to local circumstances and practices of each country	Comparability	Environmental Noise Directive 2002/49/EC, (END)
Urban Centre	A cluster of contiguous grid cells of 1 km ² (excluding diagonals) with a population density of at least 1.500 inhabitants per km ² and collectively a minimum population of 50.000 inhabitants after gap-filling.	Comparable		(Dijkstra et al., 2019)

For the analysis, information from FUA - core city (polygons of land use and land cover as well as population data) and noise contour maps are used as input data.

The intersections between urban centres and END agglomerations may result in complex analysis situations due to the abovementioned delineations.

As shown in Figure 2.3, there is not necessarily a one-to-one relationship. In Riga's case, the delineations corresponding to END agglomerations cover the complete urban centre. In the examples for Mannheim or Stockholm, there is more than one END agglomeration covering part of the urban centre (noise information does not cover the northern part of the urban centre because it is outside the END agglomeration). However, the case of one END agglomeration covering more than one urban centre is also found in the dataset, as seen in Figure 2.3 for Eindhoven.

This discrepancy between the extent of the urban centre and the coverage of noise assessments implies an area where the quietness assessment could not be conducted.

On average, 91.5% of urban centre areas are covered by noise data and the Urban Atlas polygons. The distribution of this coverage is detailed in Figure 2.4 and summarised as follows:

- **7 urban centres (3%)** have less than 50% of their area covered.
- **16 urban centres (7%)** have between 50% and 75% of their area covered.
- **46 urban centres (19%)** have between 75% and 90% of their area covered.
- **67 urban centres (28%)** have between 90% and 98% of their area covered.
- **100 urban centres (42%)** have nearly complete coverage, with between 99% and 100% of their area included.

This data highlights a significant variation in coverage, with most urban centres achieving high levels of data availability for the analysis.

Incomplete coverage can introduce bias into the results. To address this issue, we thoroughly checked for outliers in each parameter analysed (see Section 2.6 for the complete list of parameters). This step was crucial to ensure that any outliers identified did not correspond to an urban centre with incomplete coverage. In cases where outliers corresponded to urban centres with incomplete coverage, we excluded them from the analysis. By doing so, we aimed to maintain the integrity and reliability of our findings, minimising potential biases introduced by incomplete data.

The areas of the urban centres that are not covered by an END agglomeration have been excluded from the analysis, and the percentage of urban centre area covered with data has been added to the summary table for each urban centre. The obtained results will only refer to the area covered.

Figure 2.3 Example of the intersection between urban centres and END agglomerations

Figure 2.4 Percentage of the urban centre covered by noise data (END) and green areas (Urban Atlas) by country

2.4 Delineation of potential Quiet Green Areas (GQA)

This chapter describes the data and methodology to delineate quiet green areas (GQA). Two steps are needed :

- Delineation of green urban areas (GUA) by selecting Urban Atlas classes « green urban areas (code 14100)» and « forest (code 31000) ». According to the definition of Urban Atlas, these classes are considered equivalent to public parks and, therefore, would be preferred for the population to take a walk. Especially at the edges of cities, distinguishing between "green urban areas" and forests can be challenging. For this reason, the Urban Atlas class "forests" was also included in the analysis.
- Identification of GUA that are quiet by overlaying road noise contour maps and selecting those areas below 55 dB L_{den}.

2.4.1 Data sources

Spatial data analysis consistently focuses on ensuring the data's suitability for the study and the comprehensiveness of its geographic coverage. The urban delineations in this study are derived from various sources of information with differing spatial resolutions (see section 2.3).

- **Urban Atlas 2018 (UA)** high-resolution land use and land cover data with integrated population estimates for 788 Functional Urban Areas (FUA) with more than 50,000 inhabitants for the 2018 reference year in EEA38 countries and the United Kingdom. Contains population estimates for reference year 2018 at polygon level. This is the latest available data (the 2021 update will come in 2025).
- **Agglomerations** with populations exceeding 100,000 inhabitants. Delineation from Environmental Noise Directive, 2002/49/EC (END).
- **Noise contour maps** for the round of noise mapping of 2022 for road traffic noise inside END agglomerations delivered up to September 2024. This data allows us to differentiate between quiet and non-quiet areas, setting the threshold at 55 dB L_{den} . Noise contour maps inside urban areas are only reported by member states voluntarily.

2.4.2 Methodology

The first step in the analysis is characterising quiet green areas within the urban centres by excluding green areas intersecting noise contour maps $\geq 55\text{dB } L_{den}$ from road traffic noise. These results reflect the maximum potential available quiet green areas considering road traffic noise inside the urban centre as the source of noise. The following diagram in Figure 2.5 represents the flowchart to calculate the available quiet green urban areas inside agglomerations first and, in the second step, their accessibility (see section 2.5).

This first step results in the Overlay (intersect) of the green urban areas with road noise contour maps of at least 55 dB L_{den} . The green areas' surface intersecting with the noise contour maps are excluded (see Figure 2.6 and Figure 2.7) to leave out the quiet green areas only.

The exclusion of green urban areas can be seen in more detail in Figure 2.8, where road traffic noise contour maps of at least 55 dB L_{den} intersect with green urban areas. As a result, the surface that intersects with the noise contour maps is considered a noisy area. Therefore, those areas are excluded from the calculation of the percentage of quiet green areas at the urban centre level and the accessibility analysis.

Figure 2.5 Flowchart to calculate the accessibility of quiet green urban areas inside agglomerations

The green areas' surface intersecting with the noise contour maps are excluded (see Figure 2.6 and Figure 2.7) to leave out the quiet green areas only.

Figure 2.6 Green urban areas 1938 ha (left). Quiet green areas 1105 ha (right) in the urban centre of Bordeaux, France

Figure 2.7 Surface of green urban areas with noise levels above 55dB L_{den} excluded (in red)

Figure 2.8 Green urban areas inside noise contour maps (left) and green urban areas excluded for being inside noise contour maps >55dB L_{den} (right)

However, as described in section 2.3, the delineations between urban centres and END agglomerations are not coincident (see Figure 2.8), and other green urban areas are also excluded from the analysis.

Figure 2.9 shows the situation where the urban centre has some areas not covered by the END agglomeration. An area of 48.98 hectares within the urban centre (in a red square plot) exceeds the END agglomeration limits, so information on noise contour maps is unavailable. Consequently, the 8.86 hectares of green urban areas within these zones will be labelled as "No data" and excluded from the accessibility analysis and from the calculation of the percentage of quiet green areas at the urban centre level due to the absence of noise information.

Figure 2.9 Urban centre areas outside the END agglomeration area and not covered by road noise contour maps

2.5 Streets covered by noise contour bands

2.5.1 Overview

An important factor that may influence the results related to quiet green areas is the extent to which noise contour bands cover the total street network in the urban centre. According to the Environmental Noise Directive (END), Member States must provide information on all streets and roads within agglomerations. However, some Member States do not map smaller streets. The exact reason for this partial mapping is not known but it may be because cities use a specific traffic threshold or road category for selecting the roads included in the noise maps. Another reason could be that smaller roads are systematically excluded, as their traffic noise levels are assumed to be below 55 dB L_{den} .

To assess the percentage of streets for which Member States have provided noise contour bands, the street network from OpenStreetMap (OSM) has been selected as the ground truth against which the existing information related to strategic noise maps will be compared.

However, there may be some limitations in using the OSM. These include the possibility that some smaller streets may not be mapped, different time alignment compared to END reporting year, and the fact that Member States may have used different street sources for their street networks when developing strategic noise maps. Despite these limitations, OSM is currently the best open-source information available for analysing the urban centres included in this report. Therefore, the final results must account for these differences when interpreting the outcomes.

2.5.2 Methodology

The analysis of the coverage of the OSM network by the noise contour bands requires the following data sets:

1. **Noise contour maps** for road traffic noise corresponding to the 2022 round of noise mapping inside END agglomerations and delivered up to September 2024. The noise contour maps are reported voluntarily by the Member States and map those areas ≥ 55 dB L_{den} .
2. **Urban Centres**. Consists of contiguous grid cells with a density of at least 1.500 inhabitants per km². An Urban Centre has a population of at least 50.000 inhabitants.
3. **Open Street Map (OSM)**. This is a collaborative project that creates and provides free geographic data and mapping. Cartographic components are systematised by a consistent hierarchical system of tags.

The methodology is summarised in Figure 2.10 and can be described as follows:

- Data harvesting of the different components required for the analysis:
 - Delineation of Urban Centres (see also 2.4.1).
 - Noise contour maps for the selected Urban Centres (see also 2.4.1).
 - Open Street Map for selected Urban Centres.
- Selection of relevant elements:
 - Noise contour bands equal to or greater than 55 dB L_{den} .
 - Selection of streets with road traffic from OSM. Then, streets with the following tags are excluded since they are associated with pedestrian areas: 'service', 'cycleway', 'footway', 'living street', 'pedestrian', 'path', and 'steps'.
- Intersection of selected noise contour bands and OSM roads and streets with road traffic.
- Calculation of final statistics:
 - Length of OSM streets with road traffic

- Length of OSM streets covered by noise contour bands
- Percentage of OSM streets covered by noise contour maps.

The final statistics obtained refer to the lengths of OSM streets and percentage of OSM street coverage in the intersection between the urban centre and the corresponding END agglomeration as it is explained in section 2.3.

Figure 2.10 Workflow to calculate the percentage of roads covered by noise contour maps

2.5.3 Quality check

A data quality procedure has also been run to ensure that the results obtained accurately follow the established methodology. This process includes reviewing intermediate data. The review of the results obtained in GIS analysis is crucial to ensure the accuracy, completeness, and validity of the overall analysis. By systematically reviewing the results obtained in GIS analysis, it is possible to identify and address any errors, inconsistencies, or limitations early in the process, thereby improving the overall reliability and credibility of the analysis results.

The quality check assessment was carried out through a structured approach as detailed below:

- **Data Quality Assessment.** Verify the quality of the input data. This includes checking for accuracy, completeness, consistency, and resolution. Use metadata provided with the data sources to understand their limitations and characteristics.
- **Data Pre-processing.** Check for any errors or inconsistencies in the pre-processing steps, such as data cleaning, projection transformations, and attribute normalization.

- **Spatial Analysis.** Evaluate the intermediate spatial analysis results, such as spatial overlays and attribute selection accuracy.
- Verify that spatial operations have been performed correctly and that the results align with the expected outcomes based on the analysis objectives.
- **Spatial quality check.** Visualize the results using maps, charts, and graphs: ensure that the visual representation accurately reflects the results obtained from the analysis. Also visualize the intermediate results using maps, charts and graphs to identify anomalies and outliers

2.5.4 Results

On average, 70.7% of the street network in urban centres is covered by noise contour bands. However, coverage varies widely (Figure 2.11), ranging from 28.9% in New Wulmstorf, Germany, to nearly complete coverage (99%) in several urban centres, including Angers, Caen, Martigues, and Besançon in France; Vitoria-Gasteiz in Spain; Poruba in Czechia; and Lemesos and Lefkosia in Cyprus. As mentioned, OSM has some limitations, resulting in no urban centres achieving 100% coverage.

Figure 2.11 Histogram of street coverage by noise contour maps (in %)

In fact, there is a considerable variation in noise contour band coverage across countries (Figure 2.12). On average, Cyprus and France have the highest percentage of coverage, meaning that a large proportion of their OSM urban street network with road traffic is covered by noise contour bands ≥ 55 dB L_{den} . In contrast, Norway, Malta, and Portugal have the lowest street coverage by noise contour bands.

The position of countries relative to the European average does not reveal a clear geographic pattern. For example, while some Mediterranean urban centres are in countries with a high percentage of street coverage (e.g., Cyprus, Spain and France), others fall on the lower end of the spectrum (e.g., Croatia and Malta). Similarly, there is a contrasting situation in Scandinavia, where Sweden has a higher percentage of street coverage than Norway.

Beyond these differences between countries, there is also notable variability within individual countries, suggesting that no single factor fully explains the observed differences in OSM street coverage by noise contour bands. Germany, Spain and Norway exhibit the highest levels of internal variation, with a coefficient of variation (CV) exceeding 20%, indicating substantial differences in noise coverage among their urban centres. One factor that partially explains this variability is the number of urban centres analysed, which shows a weak correlation ($R^2 = 0.23$). Additionally, two other potential explanatory factors—city size and capital city status— have been explored, but found no significant relationship with the observed differences in street coverage.

Based on the available information, two possible explanations for the variability within countries can be proposed: (1) smaller streets may not have been included in mapping the noise contour bands, or (2) streets without noise contour bands likely have noise levels below 55 dB L_{den} , the reporting threshold established by the Environmental Noise Directive (END). At this stage, there is insufficient information to determine whether one explanation, the other, or a combination of both, accounts for the observed results.

One might question how OSM street coverage by noise contour bands affects the estimated extent and accessibility of quiet green areas.

Figure 2.12 Coverage of streets with road traffic by noise contour bands (%) across countries. The reference line indicates the average coverage for all 233 urban centres included in the analysis

The data show a negative relationship between the percentage of streets covered by noise contour bands and the percentage of quiet green areas—urban centres with lower OSM street coverage tend to have a higher proportion of quiet green spaces (Figure 2.13). However, the low R^2 value (0.19) indicates that street coverage alone accounts for only a small portion of the variability in quiet and green areas availability. This suggests that other factors are also relevant.

Figure 2.13 Relationship between the percentage of OSM streets covered by noise contour bands and the percentage of green areas classified as quiet ($R^2 = 0.19$, $p < 0.0001$)

The other parameters related to quiet green areas, such as the share of quiet green areas as a percentage of total land area and the share of the population having access to quiet green areas, have a significant but weak relationship with the percentage of streets covered by noise contour bands ($R^2 < 0.1$).

Since street coverage only accounts for part of the variability in the percentage of quiet green areas, we aimed to develop a statistical model incorporating additional relevant factors for which data is available. This model will help us better evaluate the impact of street coverage.

The additional factors considered are the specific country and the overall percentage of green areas. The importance of these factors is further elaborated on in *Section 3*. Results indicate that the percentage of quiet green areas varies significantly by country, and there is a statistically significant correlation between the total amount of green areas and the proportion of quiet green areas.

To combine the three factors -country, percentage of green areas and coverage of streets by noise contour maps, a linear mixed model has been developed according to the following structure:

- Dependent variable: percentage of green areas that are quiet
- Fixed effects (continuous variables):
 - Percentage of streets covered by noise contour bands
 - Percentage of green urban areas
- Random effect (categorical):
 - Country

The model was calculated with the R package lmerTest.

Figure 2.14 Output of the linear mixed model. PercGreenQuietAreas refers to the percentage of green areas that are quiet; PercentageCovered refers to the percentage of OSM streets covered by noise contour bands; pcntGreen_Total refers to the percentage of green urban areas

```
Linear mixed model fit by REML. t-tests use Satterthwaite's method ['lmerModLmerTest']
Formula: PercGreenQuietArea ~ PercentageCovered_UCAG + pcntGreen_total + (1 | ctry_code)
Data: s_data

REML criterion at convergence: 1848.6

scaled residuals:
   Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
-2.57673 -0.59010  0.07099  0.55931  2.57645

Random effects:
 Groups   Name      Variance Std.Dev.
ctry_code (Intercept)  60.06    7.75
Residual              145.54   12.06
Number of obs: 233, groups: ctry_code, 22

Fixed effects:
              Estimate Std. Error      df t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)    95.30433    6.09335 175.38225  15.641 < 2e-16 ***
PercentageCovered_UCAG -0.71789    0.07194 204.03061  -9.979 < 2e-16 ***
pcntGreen_total    0.90667    0.16703 221.85671   5.428 1.49e-07 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Correlation of Fixed Effects:
              (Intr) PC_UCA
PrcntC_UCAG -0.861
pcntGrn_ttl -0.405  0.031
```

The results of the linear mixed model indicate a reasonable fit, as evidenced by the residuals, which are almost symmetrically distributed around zero (refer to the *Scaled residuals* in in Figure 2.14). The range falls within the expected limits of approximately ±2.58 for normally distributed residuals, suggesting that there are no extreme outliers present.

All the factors included in the model contribute to explaining the differences in the percentage of quiet green areas between urban centers. Specifically, the country factor accounts for about 29.2% of these differences, as inferred from the variance values (refer to *variance* under *Random effects* in in Figure 2.14). Additionally, the percentage of total green areas and the percentage of the street network covered by noise contour maps are both significant predictors, with p-values less than 0.001 (see *Fixed*

effects in Figure 2.14). This significance indicates that both factors have an impact on the percentage of quiet green areas.

The percentage of total green area shows a positive correlation and is more significant than street coverage. Conversely, the model's output also indicates that when all other factors are held constant, a 10% increase in the percentage of streets covered by noise contour bands will lead to a 7,2 % decrease in quiet green areas (see *Estimate* value under *Fixed effects* in Figure 2.14).

Figure 2.15 illustrates the differences between the actual values (shown in blue) and the estimated values according to the linear mixed model (shown in red), along with the associated confidence intervals (represented by the light red shaded area). The estimated values indicate the percentage of quiet green areas in each urban center, assuming a street coverage of 100%.

In this model, the effect of street coverage by noise contour maps is not isolated—it is influenced by the specific country and the overall proportion of green areas in the urban centre. These factors interact to shape the final estimations, explaining the differences between predicted and actual values. Moreover, the linear mixed model exhibits a smoothing effect, which captures the general trend while filtering out noise and outliers.

We compared the estimated percentages of quiet green areas to the actual values to assess the potential impact of street coverage. According to the linear mixed model, if urban centers had a street coverage of 100%, the estimated percentage of quiet green areas in Europe would decrease by only 0.7% compared to the actual value, which is not statistically significant.

At the country level, the most significant decline in the estimated average percentage of quiet green areas is seen in Estonia, with a reduction of 9.5% when comparing estimated versus actual data. Other notable decreases include Norway, with a 5.7% reduction; Austria, at 3.4%; and Denmark, at 3.0%. For all other countries, the differences between estimated and actual values are equal to or less than 1%. While these differences were not significant, Estonia's case approached the threshold of significance with a probability of 0.06.

As illustrated in Figure 2.15, only a few urban centres have actual values (represented in blue) that fall outside the confidence interval of the estimated values (depicted in light red). This accounts for the lack of significance observed in the differences in averages at both the European and national levels.

In summary, most of the observed differences between actual and predicted data fall within the confidence interval. Therefore, the impact of the coverage of noise contour maps on the percentage of quiet green areas is measurable but has a relatively small impact. It also highlights that actual differences of 5-10% in the quiet green areas may not be significant.

These results relate to the percentage of quiet green areas, which is the indicator that is more dependent on street coverage. Therefore, for the other parameters (see section 2.7), it is expected that the impact on the final results would be lower.

Figure 2.15 Relationship between percentage of streets covered by noise contour maps (Coverage) and percentage of quiet green areas in 233 urban centres. Blue indicates actual data; in red, it is estimated values from the mixed linear model; the red area corresponds to the confidence interval of the estimation

2.6 Accessibility to Quiet Green Areas

This section outlines the data and methodology used to calculate accessibility to Quiet Green Areas (GQAs) through the following intermediate steps:

- Define service areas as streets that can be reached within a 400-meter walking distance from a GQA.
- Intersection with Population Polygons: Overlay the service areas with Urban Atlas population polygons to determine the population a GQA serves within a 400-meter walk.
- Calculation of Accessible Area: Compute the accessible, quiet green area based on the intersection of results.

2.6.1 Data sources

This analysis identifies accessibility to quiet green urban areas within urban centres using the following data sources.

- **Potential quiet green urban areas** in the urban centre (14100 Green urban areas and 31000 Forest below the threshold of 55dB L_{den} for road traffic noise).
- **Road network data.** This analysis requires a road network that contains attributes to enable the selection of streets accessible to pedestrians. TomTom Multinet data in 2019 has been used. The street network dataset designed to cover all relevant streets in the urban areas is taken into consideration for evaluating pedestrian access to green urban areas: street

segments that are considered walkable, predominantly excluding motorways, have been chosen.

- **Population estimates** for reference year 2018 at polygon level from Urban Atlas 2018.

2.6.2 Methodology

The diagram in Figure 2.5 represents the flowchart to calculate, first, the available quiet green urban areas inside agglomerations (explained in section 2.4) and, in a second step, its accessibility, which is detailed in the current section.

Overview

The proposed methodology follows and adapts the methodology developed and described in (Poelman, H et al. 2018). The first step in calculating the accessibility to green urban areas is to define the threshold of walking time or distance from residential areas to green urban areas. In previous studies (Poelman, 2018; Sáinz de la Maza et al., 2019), the criterion of 10 minutes on foot was used, but recently, this criterion has been modified to 400 m walking distance following the recommendations of UN-Habitat (UN-Habitat 2020). UN-Habitat defined an acceptable walking distance to open public spaces of 400 meters - equivalent to a 5-minute walk as a practical and realistic threshold for all groups of people. This analysis also implements this threshold of 400 meters distance. The proximity parameter used has been aligned with the SDG 11.7.1 metadata from UN-Habitat. These metadata suggest a 400-meter walk to define proximity to open and public areas, of which green urban areas and quiet green urban areas are part.

The details of the processing steps are described below.

Delineation of service areas

To calculate accessibility, service areas from the quiet green urban areas need to be generated (Figure 2.16). A network service area is a region that encompasses all accessible streets (that is, streets that are within a specified walking distance). For instance, the 400m service area for a point on a network includes all the streets that can be reached within 400m from that point. This means that we need to establish access points to the quiet green urban areas.

To establish the access points, some alternatives were considered :

- Intersect the streets with the quiet green areas to obtain access points. This option has the advantage that these access points to the quiet green areas are realistic but leaves out of the analysis small, quiet green areas where the streets run parallel to them. To overcome this problem, a methodology could have been adopted to generate access points at certain distances for quiet green areas without street intersections in order to complement the access points from the intersection with the access points generated based on the distance to the quiet green areas.
- Generate access points every 50 m along the polygon contour. In this case, only the points located at a maximum of 25 m from the street network are kept because points situated far away from the street network are considered unsuitable to start walking from or to the park (Figure 2.16 and Figure 2.17).

The second option is adopted mainly for comparability purposes between products, as it is the methodology adopted by DG Regio.

A service area of 400 m walking distance has been created for each defined access point. All access service areas belonging to the access points of the same quiet green area have been dissolved to keep the park's characteristics (i.e. its surface) as attributes of the service area.

Once all the service areas are created, an intersection considering all service areas is performed to determine the overlapping areas. In these overlapping areas, people have access to more than one quiet green area, and it is relevant to identify them if the assessment to which surface of quiet green urban area people have access to is going to be performed.

Figure 2.16 Quiet green urban areas, access points and service areas at 400 meters

Figure 2.17 Detail of quiet green urban area, access points and service area at 400 m

Figure 2.18 shows the detail of the quiet green area and its access points. On the right part of the figure, the noise contour maps ≥ 55 dB L_{den} from roads have been added to display the reduction of the surface of the green area when analysing quietness in green urban areas.

The accessibility is calculated to the quiet, green urban areas only.

Figure 2.18 Accessibility points to potential green urban areas quiet compared with green urban areas (Left, green background colors). The same area showing noise contour bands ≥ 55 dB L_{den} (Right)

Calculation of population having access to GQA

In order to calculate the population that has access to quiet green areas, the service areas calculated before are further intersected with the Urban Atlas population polygons.

The population calculated in the intersecting service area is weighted by the proportion of the Urban Atlas polygon that overlaps the service area (see Figure 2.19) to take into account how much of the whole urban centre population is represented in the service area.

Figure 2.19 Overlap of service areas (SA) with Urban Atlas polygons.

The formula applied to calculate the accessibility to quiet green urban areas at the urban centre level :

$$Population\ with\ access\ to\ GQA = \sum \frac{Area\ of\ the\ intersection\ SA\ and\ UA}{Total\ area\ of\ the\ UA\ polygon} \cdot UA\ Population$$

Where: GQA, Quiet green area; SA, Service area; UA, Urban Atlas.

The population of the service area is calculated by weighting the population of each Urban Atlas (UA) polygon based on the proportion of its area that intersects with the service area (SA).

The total population with access to quiet green urban areas is obtained by summing up the weighted populations for all quiet green areas identified in the city.

Calculation of accessible area (population-weighted median area)

Accessible area measures the typical size of such spaces that can be reached within a 400 m walk. It is calculated by sorting the quiet green areas by size and then identifying the area that divides the population into two equal groups, with half of the population having access to areas larger than the median and half of the population having access to smaller areas (population-weighted median area).

The following data is needed :

- **Population Data:** The total population that has access to each GQA.
- **Accessible Surface Data:** The size of quiet green urban areas accessible to the population per each green urban area (in hectares).

In simpler terms, the weighted median gives the size of a typical quiet green area but with extra consideration about how many people would benefit from it. The weighted median is a robust summary measure that considers the relative importance of observations through weights, such as population served. It is less influenced by extreme values than the weighted mean, making it a fairer and more representative central value.

2.7 Statistics and Indicators

The indicators calculated in this study are crucial for assessing the condition of quiet green areas across Europe. They provide valuable insights into the current status of these spaces, enabling a deeper understanding of their role and significance. Additionally, incorporating comparability by using urban centres as a reference enhances the analysis and provides a robust standard for these areas. Table 2.3

Indicators calculated in the analysis per each urban centre Table 2.3 contains all indicators calculated in the analysis and their description.

Table 2.3 Indicators calculated in the analysis per each urban centre

Field	Description
uc_code	Code of the urban centre
uc_name	Urban centre name
ctry_code	Country code
TotalUCAreaHa	Urban centre area (Ha)
UC_UA_AreaHa	Area of the Urban Centre with Urban Atlas data
UC_UA_Pop	Total population in Urban Centre from Urban Atlas

Field	Description
UC_UA_NCM_AreaHa	Area of the intersection of Urban centre, Urban Atlas and END agglomeration (ha)
UC_UA_NCM_Pop	Population of the intersection of Urban centre, Urban Atlas and END agglomeration. The population is calculated from Urban Atlas attributes
Perc_coverage_Area	Percentage of area covered in the study relative to the reference area (UC) (%)
Perc_coverage_Pop	Population in coverage area relative to the reference data where Urban Centre intersects Urban Atlas (%)
TotalGreen_urbc_ncm_Ha	Total green area in the study area (Ha)
TotalGreenQuietAreaHa	Total Quiet green Area in Study area (Ha)
TotalGQAPop	Population with access to Quiet green areas (inhab.)
PercGreenQuietArea	Percentage of total Quiet green area relative to the total green in the study area (%)
PercGreenQuietPop	Percentage of population with access to GQA relative to total population in the study area (%)
weighted_median_Ha	Weighted median of quiet green areas relative to population (Ha)
TotalGreenAreaHa	Total green area in urban centre (Ha)
green_excludedHa	Green area without noise contour maps (Ha)

3 Results

3.1 Accessibility to GQA (share of the population)

Based on the analysis, 65% of the urban population has access to green areas. However, this percentage drops to just 34% (81,9 M inhabitants in 233 urban centres) when considering only green areas that are also quiet. This indicates that while many green spaces are accessible, road traffic noise often impacts them, potentially diminishing their restorative benefits.

However, as seen in Figure 3.1, there is considerable diversity in accessibility between urban centres. Factors such as geographic context, population density, the availability of green spaces, and the level at which urban centres are covered by noise reporting contribute to this variation.

The Netherlands and Northern European countries have higher accessibility to quiet green areas, averaging between 45% and 50%. Notably, Helsinki stands out, with 95% of its population accessing these areas. These results are also consistent with the fact that cities in the North and West of Europe have more green spaces, in total, within their area than cities in Southern and Eastern Europe (EEA,

2023). Conversely, smaller countries such as Cyprus, Belgium, and Malta, as well as Ireland, have lower accessibility, with country averages below 22%. Other countries below the European average are Portugal (only one urban centre), France, Germany, Luxembourg, Poland and Croatia.

As described in Section 2.4, reported noise contour maps do not cover the entire street network of urban centres. On average, 70.7% of streets are covered, and in 6.8% of urban centres, coverage falls below 50%. According to the Environmental Noise Directive (END), Member States must provide information on all streets and roads within agglomerations. However, some Member States have communicated that smaller streets are sometimes systematically excluded, as their traffic noise levels are assumed to be below 55 dB L_{den} . The analysis presented in section 2.4 shows that the street coverage has a statistically significant impact on the quiet green areas. However, the coverage only explains part of the differences in the percentage of quiet green areas, and its impact on aggregated values at the European level or by country is limited since potential differences observed are within the confidence interval. Therefore, smaller differences between countries, i.e. between 5 to 10%, may be due to the level of reporting and corresponding street coverage of the cities and should be considered cautiously.

In this general geographic context, there are some exceptions. For example, the Netherlands exhibits high accessibility to quiet green areas (49,8%), whereas Luxembourg and Belgium, neighbouring countries with high population density too, show much lower figures (26,5 and 20% respectively). This finding is consistent with the distribution of green urban areas in urban centres described by Poelman (2018). Moreover, people's exposure to road traffic noise inside agglomerations (≥ 55 dB L_{den}) is lower in the Netherlands (19,3%) than in Luxembourg (24,5%). However, Belgium has only 14% of people exposed, although the data is partially estimated (all referred data from EEA, 2020). This information relates to the number of people exposed to road noise in 2017, and the percentage is related to the total country's population.

Numbers at the city level can, however, be very different. For example, if we consider the percentage of people exposed inside agglomerations as the share of the population of the agglomerations, updated data for 2022 shows that the people exposed is 37,5% in the Netherlands, 43,9% in Belgium (partially estimated) and 80,0% in Luxembourg. It should be noted that these comparisons consider different delineations than in the present study where the percentage of accessibility to quiet green areas refers to urban centres: the percentage of people exposed to road traffic noise refers to agglomerations, as the END defines. Knowing the limitations described above, this information is helpful to explore how well the road traffic noise could contribute to explaining the differences observed in accessibility to quiet green areas between urban centres in different countries.

Another country with high accessibility to quiet green areas is Spain, which has an average accessibility of 42,4% and is situated between Northern countries like Estonia (43,8%), Latvia (42,4%) and Denmark (36,8%) . Additionally, there is significant variability within countries, especially those with multiple urban centres included in the study. For instance, Spain, with its 12 urban centres, has a coefficient of variation of 29%, while in Estonia and Denmark, the coefficient is 2,2 and 5,9 for 2 and 4 urban centres, respectively (only one urban centre is available for Latvia).

These elements underscore the importance of the local scale and factors that are challenging to capture at the European level, particularly those related to city structure and urban planning, which are out of the scope of this report. The relevance of local factors to understanding differences also highlights that the results should be considered cautiously when trying to find some generalisation.

The local factors become evident when comparing the spatial distribution of green areas and the impact of road traffic noise. Figure 3.2 provides examples of three urban centres with low accessibility (first row) and three with high accessibility (second row) to quiet green areas. The red patches indicate green areas with noise levels above the END threshold, i.e., noise levels from road traffic of at least 55 dB L_{den} . Consequently, the overall accessibility does not consider the red patches, resulting in a low accessibility value at the urban centre level due to the low acoustic quality of the existing green areas.

Figure 3.1 Share of population having access to quiet green areas within 400 m walk by country. Capitals are indicated in blue. Countries are sorted by their urban centre's accessibility median (decreasing order)

Figure 3.2 Distribution of quiet green areas (in green) and green non-quiet areas (in red) in selected urban centres. The percentage next to the city name refers to the share of the population having access to quiet green areas. The legend's label "quiet green" corresponds to the class "Green urban areas" of Urban Atlas below 55 dB L_{den} for road noise. The label "quiet forests" corresponds to the class "Forests" of Urban Atlas below 55 dB L_{den} for road noise

In the first row of Figure 3.2, corresponding to urban centres with low accessibility, we see that the coverage of green areas is smaller, and most of these areas are marked in red, indicating higher noise levels.

Although located in different geographic contexts, Lefkosia, Antwerpen, and Valletta share dense historical centres where traffic noise around green areas decreases the availability of quiet green spaces. Valletta and Nemesos (not included in the figure) are the urban centres with the lowest percentage of green areas in the urban centre (2% of the total area of urban centres, without considering the acoustic quality).

Conversely, in the second row, cities like Gijón, Stockholm, and Almere have a higher share of green areas, with more green patches and more evenly distributed, resulting in higher availability and accessibility to quiet green areas. It should be noted that there is an intermix of quiet and non-quiet areas.

Along the same line, the variability within countries suggests that national averages may not fully represent the situation for individual cities. This variability underscores the importance of local factors determining the accessibility to quiet green areas. Local policies and urban planning strategies - including noise action plans, can significantly influence the availability and distribution of these spaces. For example, cities with proactive green space policies and strong community involvement in urban planning may achieve higher accessibility rates than those without such initiatives (Skodra et al., 2020). Moreover, historical development patterns play a crucial role. Cities with a long historical development concerning urban green space may have more established and accessible green areas. Then, mobility policies modulate the acoustic quality of these green areas. Community engagement is also vital, as active participation in urban planning can lead to more tailored and effective green space solutions that meet the specific needs of residents (Mahmoud et al., 2022).

In this context, city size does not significantly correlate with accessibility to quiet green areas (Figure 3.3), indicating that a city's physical size or population does not determine how accessible these areas are to residents.

Figure 3.1 also highlights European capitals in blue. In most cases (11 out of 17 countries, 64,7%), the accessibility to quiet green areas in capitals is higher than the average in non-capital cities (Table 3.1). However, the number of countries and cities included in the analysis cannot draw definitive conclusions.

Figure 3.3 Relationship between urban centre population and population having access to quiet green areas within 400 m walk (% of the total population)

Although there is variability in the determinants that influence the accessibility to quiet green areas, the availability of these areas in the urban centre plays a role in determining its accessibility to a certain extent. Factors such as urban planning, population density, and local environmental conditions can modulate accessibility, but the presence of quiet green spaces is a fundamental prerequisite. Even the best urban planning efforts may fall short of providing adequate access to these areas without sufficient availability.

Table 3.1 Share of population having access to quiet green areas within 400 m walk by country, capital and non-capital urban centres. In bold, capitals where the share is equal or higher than non-capitals. Latvia, Luxembourg and Malta can not be compared because only information on the capital is available. Lithuania and Portugal are not included because there is no information on the corresponding capitals

Country	Number of urban centres	Share of population having access to quiet green areas	
		Capitals	Non-capitals
Austria	5	46,5	32,9
Belgium	7	27,7	20,6
Croatia	3	24,2	26,8
Cyprus	2	24,3	26,8
Czechia	10	45,8	35,4
Denmark	4	29,9	39,1
Estonia	2	45,3	42,2
Finland	6	95,1	46,0
France	28	24,2	24,1
Germany	61	29,9	28,3
Ireland	3	31,5	11,8
<i>Latvia</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>42,2</i>	
<i>Luxembourg</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>26,5</i>	
<i>Malta</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>22,0</i>	
Netherlands	28	34,5	51,5
Norway	4	37,7	46,6
Poland	28	25,1	28,2
Spain	15	33,0	43,0
Sweden	13	64,4	46,4
Switzerland	9	38,7	35,1

This connection is reflected in Figure 3.4. The relationship between availability and accessibility is significant ($p < 0,0001$), although the correlation coefficient is very low (0,16). This low correlation can be attributed to another critical factor: the distribution of these spaces throughout the urban centre area. Even if quiet green areas are available, their uneven distribution across a city can lead to disparities in accessibility. For instance, if green spaces are concentrated in specific neighbourhoods, residents in other areas may still lack adequate access despite the overall availability. Figure 3.5 illustrates the difference between Nice and Almere, two urban centres with similar shares of quiet green areas (12,8 and 11,8% respectively) but contrasting accessibility. Due to Nice's geographic setting, encapsulated between the hills and the coast, the green areas are primarily located on the fringe, on the slopes of hills. In the Netherlands, Almere is located in a flat area with a more homogenous distribution of green urban areas and a relatively limited impact of road traffic noise.

Figure 3.4 Relationship between quiet green areas as percentage of the total area of the urban centre and share of population having access to quiet green areas within 400 m walk. (R²=0,16, p < 0,001)

Figure 3.5 Accessibility to quiet green areas in Nice and Almere. The legend's “quiet green” label corresponds to the class “Green urban areas” of Urban Atlas with road traffic noise levels below 55 dB L_{den}. The label “quiet forests” corresponds to the class “Forests” of Urban Atlas with traffic noise levels below 55 dB L_{den}. GQA, quiet green areas

The link between available quiet green areas and their accessibility can also be seen when comparing the distribution by country (Figure 3.6). Generally, countries are ordered similarly whether sorted by accessibility (Figure 3.1) or by the availability of quiet green areas (Figure 3.6).

Northern European countries tend to have a higher share of quiet green areas within urban centres (the first five countries average between 11.5% and 15.5%). The higher availability of quiet green areas translates to better accessibility for residents in these regions.

Conversely, countries like Cyprus, Malta, and Ireland are on the lower end of the spectrum, with fewer quiet green areas within their urban centres (below 3%). The limited availability of quiet green areas results in reduced accessibility for their populations.

However, there are some exceptions to this pattern, such as Spain. While the share of the population having access to quiet green areas in Spain, on average, is higher than the European average (Figure 3.1), the country ranks lower when considering the actual availability of quiet green areas (Figure 3.6).

This discrepancy suggests that despite having fewer quiet green areas overall, the structure of the cities and the distribution of green areas make these areas more accessible to their population.

However, it needs to be considered that noise contour maps data is not available for all the cities that have to report under the END. For example, in the case of Spain, only 14 out of 63 cities above 100.000 inhabitants have been reported and therefore included in the current analysis.

Figure 3.6 Quiet green areas as a percentage of the total area of the urban centre by country

Figure 3.7 Comparison of four cities representing contrasting combinations of available quiet green areas (as a percentage of total area of urban centres) and share of the population having access to quiet green areas. Barcharts provide information on (from left to right): number of inhabitants of the urban centre; GQA (% urban centre), quiet green areas as a percentage of the total area of the urban centre; the share of the population having access to quiet green areas within a 400 m walk, and accessible area (ha). (GQA equals to quiet green areas). The legend's "quiet green" label corresponds to the class "Green urban areas" of Urban Atlas with road traffic noise levels below 55 dB L_{den}. The label "quiet forests" corresponds to the class "Forests" of Urban Atlas with traffic noise levels below 55 dB L_{den}. Urban centres are ordered by the share of the population having access to quiet green areas

Groningen

Zagreb

Limerick

Four cities have been selected to exemplify the differences in the availability and accessibility of quiet green areas (Figure 3.7). Helsinki features a homogeneous distribution of quiet green areas, resulting in high accessibility. Groningen and Zagreb are similar regarding the availability of quiet green areas. However, in Zagreb, these areas are mainly concentrated in the periphery because the green areas in the centre exceed the noise thresholds (indicated as red patches on the map). On the lower end, Limerick has fewer green areas, mostly affected by road traffic noise

3.2 Accessibility to GQA (population-weighted median area)

Figure 3.7 introduces an additional parameter, which is the accessible area. Accessible area measures the typical size of such spaces that can be reached within a 400 m walk. It is calculated by sorting the quiet green areas by size and then identifying the area that divides the population into two equal groups, with half of the population having access to areas larger than the median and half of the population having access to smaller areas (population-weighted median area).

The size and distribution of patches of quiet green areas strongly influence this parameter. For instance, among the four urban centres presented in Figure 3.7, Zagreb has the largest accessible area (3,8 ha). However, the percentage of quiet green areas in Zagreb is only 7,8%, considerably lower than Helsinki's 16.5%.

In summary, despite Zagreb's larger accessible area, its limited percentage of quiet green areas, coupled with their peripheral distribution, means fewer people can benefit from them than cities with more evenly distributed green areas. By contrast, in Helsinki, more people can access quiet green spaces despite their smaller size due to their more balanced distribution.

Planning for cities with better accessibility to quiet green areas has to consider all these results. Some constraints inherent to the cities are related to their history and geographic setting. These elements are difficult to change, and any intervention in this aspect would require time and resources that are only feasible in the mid and long term -if feasible. An analysis of 919 European cities (lungman et al., 2024) highlighted that greener and less densely populated cities tend to have lower mortality rates, lower air pollution levels, and a reduced urban heat island effect. In contrast, compact, high-density cities have higher mortality rates, less green space, poorer air quality, and a stronger urban heat island effect but lower greenhouse gas emissions per capita. Therefore, preserving the acoustic quality of existing green areas is probably one of the most efficient measures, as the END stresses. Also, developing new green areas will take some time, considering the time required for growing of vegetation.

Jiang (2024) assesses the potential health benefits of reducing noise annoyance from road traffic by increasing green space exposure in European agglomerations. The findings show that achieving at least 0.5 hectares within a 300 m distance or a 5-minute walk from home could reduce the number of highly noise-annoyed adults by up to 9.6% due to road traffic noise, potentially preventing almost one million highly annoyed adults in Europe.

4 Conclusions

Based on previous studies, the methodology presented in this report is a helpful tool for the spatial assessment of the accessibility to quiet green areas in urban centres. The methodology facilitates the comparison between cities and provides a deeper insight into the different neighbourhoods of the urban centres, which is relevant to understanding the different accessibility patterns.

Input data related to noise is critical for the assessment. Therefore, Member States should be encouraged to provide noise contour maps, which are voluntary according to the END specifications. A broader geographic coverage would help better understand the situation in European cities and the number of people with a positive health impact from quiet green areas.

From the methodological perspective, analysing the streets covered by reported noise data may help to understand to what extent differences within and between countries are influenced by varying approaches, such as the systematic exclusion of smaller streets. In case of uneven alignment between noise contour maps and the street network, this disparity could impact the results obtained, the comparisons drawn, and the differences observed, particularly at the neighbourhood level. The findings of this report indicate that the incomplete street network coverage by noise contour maps has a statistically significant impact on the percentage of quiet green areas. In fact, urban centres with smaller coverage tend to have a higher percentage of quiet green areas as fewer streets are mapped as 'noisy'. However, street coverage is just one factor influencing the overall variability of quiet green areas. Its impact is limited, especially when analysing data at the European and country levels. Differences of 5–10% between countries should be interpreted cautiously, as they may be influenced by variations in street coverage. Among all indicators, the percentage of quiet green areas is the most affected by street coverage, while the impact on other indicators is much smaller.

The study focuses exclusively on road traffic noise, the predominant source of environmental noise inside and outside urban areas in Europe. Therefore, the results indicate the maximum accessibility, which would likely decrease if the analysis included other noise sources, such as railways and, to a lesser extent, aircraft noise.

Cities have two complementary strategies to increase the accessibility to quiet green areas: protecting existing green areas to preserve good acoustic quality and/or increasing green areas in the city. The second option may not be feasible, particularly in denser historical urban centres with little or no vacant land. Therefore, protecting existing green areas from traffic noise is key to improving the situation in cities, as highlighted by the END. Moreover, quiet green areas should be distributed in a way that provides accessibility to most people, avoiding differences within the city that may reinforce social inequalities.

The results revealed some general trends but should be interpreted with caution due to the significant influence of local factors, particularly those related to noise patterns, distribution of patches of green areas and noise map coverage. Northern countries generally exhibit a more uniform distribution of green spaces with good acoustic quality, making them accessible to a more significant portion of the population. In contrast, smaller and denser countries like Cyprus, Malta, and Belgium rank lower regarding accessibility to quiet green areas.

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Name	Reference
DG Regio	Directorate-general Regional and Urban Policy	Regional and urban policy
EEA	European Environment Agency	www.eea.europa.eu
END	Environmental noise directive	Directive 2002/49/EC
ETC/ATNI	European Topic Centre on Air Pollution, Transport, Noise and Industrial Pollution	ETC/ATNI
FUA	Functional Urban Area	FUA
GQA	Quiet green areas	
GUA	Green urban areas	
OSM	Open Street Map	www.openstreetmap.org
SA	Service area	ArcGIS Pro
UAB	Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona	UAB

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Annex 1 Quiet Green Areas in Urban Centres Map Series

This Annex provides the complete list by country of the 233 urban centres included in the analysis (Table A1.1), followed by a map series of quiet green areas for each urban centre in alphabetical order.

Table A1.1 List of 233 Urban Centres by country included in the analysis

Country	Urban centre names
Austria	Graz; Innsbruck; Linz; Salzburg; Wien
Belgium	Antwerpen; Brugge; Bruxelles / Brussel; Charleroi; Gent; Leuven; Liège
Croatia	Rijeka; Split; Zagreb
Cyprus	Lefkosia; Lemesos
Czechia	Brno; Havířov; Hrabuvka; Liberec; Olomouc; Ostrava; Plzeň; Poruba; Praha; Ústí nad Labem
Denmark	Aalborg; Århus; København; Odense
Estonia	Tallinn; Tartu
Finland	Helsinki; Jyväskylä; Lahti; Oulu / Uleåborg; Tampere / Tammerfors; Turku / Åbo
France	Aix-en-Provence; Angers; Arras; Besançon; Bordeaux; Brest; Caen; Clermont-Ferrand; Dunkerque; Grenoble; Lens; Les Clayes-sous-Bois; Limoges; Lyon; Mantes en Yvelines; Marseille; Martigues / Port-de-Bouc; Maurepas / Montigny-le-Bretonneux; Nantes; Nice; Paris; Poissy; Reims; Rennes; Rouen; Saint-Etienne; Saint-Priest / Mions; Tours
Germany	Aachen; Augsburg; Berlin; Bielefeld; Bonn; Braunschweig; Bremen; Bremerhaven; Chemnitz; Darmstadt; Dresden; Düsseldorf; Erlangen; Frankfurt am Main; Freiburg im Breisgau; Fürth; Göttingen; Grövelingen / Vegesack; Halle an der Saale; Hamburg; Hanau; Hannover; Harburg; Heidelberg; Heilbronn; Hildesheim; Ingolstadt; Karlsruhe; Kassel; Kiel; Koblenz; Köln; Krefeld; Leipzig; Lübeck; Lütten Klein; Magdeburg; Mainz; Mannheim/Ludwigshafen; Moers-Rheinhausen; Mönchengladbach; München; Münster; Neu Wulmstorf / Neugraben-Fischbek / Hausbruch; Oldenburg (Oldenburg); Osnabrück; Pforzheim; Porz; Potsdam; Regensburg; Reutlingen; Rostock; Ruhrgebiet; Saarbrücken; Solingen; Stuttgart; Ulm/Neu-Ulm; Vaihingen / Möhringen; Wiesbaden; Wuppertal; Würzburg
Ireland	Cork; Dublin; Limerick
Latvia	Riga
Lithuania	Kaunas
Luxembourg	Luxembourg
Malta	Valletta
Netherlands	s-Hertogenbosch; Alkmaar; Almere; Alphen aan den Rijn; Amsterdam; Apeldoorn; Arnhem; Beverwijk/Heemskerk; Breda; Den Haag; Eindhoven; Enschede; Gouda; Groningen; Haarlem; Helmond; Hengelo; Hilversum; Leiden; Nieuwegein / IJsselstein; Nijmegen; Pijnacker-BerkelenRodenrijs; Rotterdam; Scharwoude / Heerhugowaard; Spijkenisse; Utrecht; Zoetermeer; Zwolle

Country	Urban centre names
Norway	Bergen; Oslo; Stavanger; Trondheim
Poland	Białystok; Bielsko-Biała; Bydgoszcz; Częstochowa; Elbląg; Gdańsk; Gdynia; Górnośląski Związek Metropolitalny; Gorzów Wielkopolski; Kasztelanka; Kielce; Kraków; Łódź; Lublin; Olsztyn; Opole; Płock; Poznań; Radom; Rzeszów; Szczecin; Tarnów; Toruń; Tychy; Warszawa; Włocławek; Wrocław; Zielona Góra
Portugal	Porto
Spain	Bilbao; Castellón de la Plana/Castelló de la Plana; Fuenlabrada; Gijón; León; Logroño; Madrid; Oviedo; Pamplona/Iruña; San Sebastián/Donostia; Torrejón de Ardoz; Valencia; Valladolid; Vigo; Vitoria/Gasteiz
Sweden	Borås; Göteborg; Helsingborg; Jönköping / Huskvarna; Linköping; Lund; Malmö; Norrköping; Örebro; Stockholm; Umeå; Uppsala; Västerås
Switzerland	Bern; Biel/Bienne; Lausanne; Lugano; St. Gallen; Winterthur; Zürich; Basel; Genève

's-Hertogenbosch

Green quiet areas in 's-Hertogenbosch urban centre

Kadaster, Esri, TomTom, Garmin, Foursquare, GeoTechnologies, Inc, METI/NASA, USGS

- | | |
|---|--|
| Non quiet green and forest |
| Urban centre |

's-Hertogenbosch (NL) , Inhabitants 2021: 139954
Total green area (Ha) 573.33
Total green quiet area: 170.05 (Ha); 29.66 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 87529; 61.98 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 573.33 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.19 (Ha)

Aachen

Green quiet areas in Aachen urban centre

Aachen (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 224750
Total green area (Ha) 512.1
Total green quiet area: 188.98 (Ha); 36.9 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 39934; 18.18 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 542.48 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 30.38 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.99 (Ha)

Aalborg

Green quiet areas in Aalborg urban centre

0 5 km

Non quiet green and forest	
Urban centre	

Aalborg (DK) , Inhabitants 2021: 149041
Total green area (Ha) 535.51
Total green quiet area: 347.1 (Ha); 64.82 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 44870; 35.27 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 546.28 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 10.77 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.6 (Ha)

Aix-en-Provence

Green quiet areas in Aix-en-Provence urban centre

- | | |
|---|--|
| Non quiet green and forest |
| Urban centre |

Aix-en-Provence (FR) , Inhabitants 2021: 101708
Total green area (Ha) 229.08
Total green quiet area: 137.05 (Ha); 59.83 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 17095; 17.21 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 229.08 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.73 (Ha)

Alkmaar

Green quiet areas in Alkmaar urban centre

Alkmaar (NL) , Inhabitants 2021: 98429
Total green area (Ha) 264.19
Total green quiet area: 111.03 (Ha); 42.03 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 49326; 49.06 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 264.19 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.66 (Ha)

Almere

Green quiet areas in Almere urban centre

Almere (NL) , Inhabitants 2021: 178471
Total green area (Ha) 1215.88
Total green quiet area: 578.99 (Ha); 47.62 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 132064; 74.88 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 1215.88 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.65 (Ha)

Alphen aan den Rijn

Green quiet areas in Alphen aan den Rijn urban centre

- | | |
|---|--|
| Non quiet green and forest |
| Urban centre |

Alphen aan den Rijn (NL) , Inhabitants 2021: 68947
Total green area (Ha) 192.03
Total green quiet area: 81.24 (Ha); 42.31 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 37775; 54.39 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 192.03 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.88 (Ha)

Amsterdam

Green quiet areas in Amsterdam urban centre

Amsterdam (NL) , Inhabitants 2021: 1182620
Total green area (Ha) 2035.78
Total green quiet area: 935.91 (Ha); 45.97 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 391337; 34.48 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 2111.76 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 75.98 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.3 (Ha)

Angers

Green quiet areas in Angers urban centre

Angers (FR) , Inhabitants 2021: 192541
Total green area (Ha) 636.34
Total green quiet area: 133.78 (Ha); 21.02 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 24430; 12.92 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 636.34 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.61 (Ha)

Antwerpen

Green quiet areas in Antwerpen urban centre

Antwerpen (BE) , Inhabitants 2021: 586261
Total green area (Ha) 790.44
Total green quiet area: 201.59 (Ha); 25.5 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 43597; 8.94 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 1105.92 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 315.48 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.08 (Ha)

Apeldoorn

Green quiet areas in Apeldoorn urban centre

Apeldoorn (NL) , Inhabitants 2021: 138831
Total green area (Ha) 476,46
Total green quiet area: 288.36 (Ha); 60.52 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 71720; 51.59 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 476.46 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.7 (Ha)

Århus

Green quiet areas in Århus urban centre

Esri, TomTom, Garmin, Foursquare, GeoTechnologies, Inc, METI/NASA, USGS

Århus (DK) , Inhabitants 2021: 245448
Total green area (Ha) 813.64
Total green quiet area: 603.47 (Ha); 74.17 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 89226; 37.79 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 852.89 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 39.25 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 5.74 (Ha)

Arnhem

Green quiet areas in Arnhem urban centre

Arnhem (NL) , Inhabitants 2021: 188519
Total green area (Ha) 702.87
Total green quiet area; 412.82 (Ha); 58.73 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 89246; 58.84 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 801.96 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 99.09 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.17 (Ha)

Arras

Green quiet areas in Arras urban centre

Arras (FR) , Inhabitants 2021: 63270
Total green area (Ha) 157.05
Total green quiet area: 91.54 (Ha); 58.29 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 4786; 7.18 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 157.05 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 5.4 (Ha)

Augsburg

Green quiet areas in Augsburg urban centre

Augsburg (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 335027
Total green area (Ha) 972.59
Total green quiet area: 659.04 (Ha); 67.76 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 72425; 25.62 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 1041.09 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 68.5 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 5.29 (Ha)

Basel

Green quiet areas in Basel urban centre

0 5 km

Basel (CH-DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 431525
Total green area (Ha) 1066.55
Total green quiet area: 703.04 (Ha); 65.92 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 101272; 30.58 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 1066.65 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0.1 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 6.12 (Ha)

Bergen

Green quiet areas in Bergen urban centre

0 5 km

Non quiet green and forest	
Urban centre	

Bergen (NO) , Inhabitants 2021: 237285
Total green area (Ha) 2234.35
Total green quiet area: 1959.72 (Ha); 87.71 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 81907; 41.15 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 2294.48 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 60.13 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 42.82 (Ha)

Berlin

Green quiet areas in Berlin urban centre

0 5 km

 Non quiet green and forest
 Urban centre

Berlin (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 3647479
Total green area (Ha) 9403.74
Total green quiet area: 5719.38 (Ha); 60.82 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 1046289; 29.93 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 10213.37 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 809.63 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 5.28 (Ha)

Bern

Green quiet areas in Bern urban centre

FOEN / Swiss Parks Network, swisstopo, Esri, TomTom, Garmin, Foursquare, GeoTechnologies, Inc, METI/NASA, USGS

Bern (CH) , Inhabitants 2021: 200065
Total green area (Ha) 1597.6
Total green quiet area: 1030.59 (Ha); 64.51 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 79089; 38.72 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 1597.6 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 11.35 (Ha)

Besançon

Green quiet areas in Besançon urban centre

Besançon (FR) , Inhabitants 2021: 107382
Total green area (Ha) 232.66
Total green quiet area: 151.9 (Ha); 65.29 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 22661; 20.95 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 232.66 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.43 (Ha)

Beverwijk/Heemskerk

Green quiet areas in Beverwijk/Heemskerk urban centre

Beverwijk/Heemskerk (NL) , Inhabitants 2021: 95686
Total green area (Ha) 248.58
Total green quiet area; 109.19 (Ha); 43.93 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 41749; 50.67 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 262.8 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 14.22 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.62 (Ha)

Bialystok

Green quiet areas in Bialystok urban centre

Bialystok (PL) , Inhabitants 2021: 275125
Total green area (Ha) 765.76
Total green quiet area: 551.06 (Ha); 71.96 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 68843; 24.06 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 940.73 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 174.97 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.52 (Ha)

Biel/Bienne

Green quiet areas in Biel/Bienne urban centre

Biel/Bienne (CH) , Inhabitants 2021: 67761
Total green area (Ha) 250.6
Total green quiet area: 229.66 (Ha); 91.64 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 23606; 33.88 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 251.25 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0.65 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 16.29 (Ha)

Bielefeld

Green quiet areas in Bielefeld urban centre

Bielefeld (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 172801
Total green area (Ha) 933.88
Total green quiet area: 586.93 (Ha); 62.85 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 81933; 33.72 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 933.88 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 4.06 (Ha)

Bielsko-Biala

Green quiet areas in Bielsko-Biala urban centre

Bielsko-Biala (PL) , Inhabitants 2021: 116650
Total green area (Ha) 270.6
Total green quiet area: 171.49 (Ha); 63.37 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 18550; 14.33 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 270.6 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.59 (Ha)

Bilbao

Green quiet areas in Bilbao urban centre

Bilbao (ES) , Inhabitants 2021: 766838
Total green area (Ha) 222.84
Total green quiet area: 121.16 (Ha); 54.37 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 138613; 31.36 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 690.88 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 468.04 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.24 (Ha)

Bonn

Green quiet areas in Bonn urban centre

0 5 km

Bonn (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 522767

Total green area (Ha) 1322.55

Total green quiet area: 609.85 (Ha); 46.11 (%)

People with acces to green quiet area 65404; 20.56 (%)

Green area in Urban centre 2242.71 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 920.16 (Ha)

Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 6.89 (Ha)

Borås

Green quiet areas in Borås urban centre

Borås (SE) , Inhabitants 2021: 65361
Total green area (Ha) 563.43
Total green quiet area: 315.34 (Ha); 55.97 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 23614; 35.13 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 563.43 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 8.48 (Ha)

Bordeaux

Green quiet areas in Bordeaux urban centre

0 5 km

Bordeaux (FR) , Inhabitants 2021: 690408
Total green area (Ha) 1929.19
Total green quiet area: 1105.04 (Ha); 57.28 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 173592; 26.38 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 1938.05 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 8.86 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.08 (Ha)

Braunschweig

Green quiet areas in Braunschweig urban centre

Braunschweig (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 184746
Total green area (Ha) 742.48
Total green quiet area: 227.06 (Ha); 30.58 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 45806; 24.22 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 742.48 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.25 (Ha)

Breda

Green quiet areas in Breda urban centre

Breda (NL) , Inhabitants 2021: 132156
Total green area (Ha) 269.24
Total green quiet area: 112.04 (Ha); 41.61 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 55155; 41.14 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 275.49 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 6.25 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.09 (Ha)

Bremen

Green quiet areas in Bremen urban centre

Bremen (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 416970
Total green area (Ha) 889.25
Total green quiet area: 347.23 (Ha); 39.05 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 94776; 22.13 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 890.35 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 1.1 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.69 (Ha)

Bremerhaven

Green quiet areas in Bremerhaven urban centre

Bremerhaven (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 110291
Total green area (Ha) 473.48
Total green quiet area: 207.64 (Ha); 43.85 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 33188; 30.55 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 478.21 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 4.73 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.69 (Ha)

Brest

Green quiet areas in Brest urban centre

Brest (FR) , Inhabitants 2021: 141056
Total green area (Ha) 328.57
Total green quiet area: 207.7 (Ha); 63.21 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 65454; 48.05 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 328.57 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.8 (Ha)

Brno

Green quiet areas in Brno urban centre

0 5 km

Brno (CZ) , Inhabitants 2021: 313019

Total green area (Ha) 1503.14

Total green quiet area: 1156.12 (Ha); 76.91 (%)

People with acces to green quiet area 90466; 30.01 (%)

Green area in Urban centre 1536.62 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 33.48 (Ha)

Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 5.46 (Ha)

Brugge

Green quiet areas in Brugge urban centre

Brugge (BE) , Inhabitants 2021: 94947
Total green area (Ha) 364.67
Total green quiet area: 235.65 (Ha); 64.62 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 33610; 34.16 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 371.17 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 6.5 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.13 (Ha)

Bruxelles / Brussel

Green quiet areas in Bruxelles / Brussel urban centre

0 5 km

	Non quiet green and forest		
	Urban centre		

Bruxelles / Brussel (BE) , Inhabitants 2021: 1342992
Total green area (Ha) 1985.21
Total green quiet area: 1082.94 (Ha); 54.55 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 330383; 27.67 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 2610.09 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 624.88 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.88 (Ha)

Bydgoszcz

Green quiet areas in Bydgoszcz urban centre

Bydgoszcz (PL) , Inhabitants 2021: 244321
Total green area (Ha) 654.76
Total green quiet area: 235.56 (Ha); 35.98 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 37780; 14.26 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 921.06 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 266.3 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 6.09 (Ha)

Caen

Green quiet areas in Caen urban centre

Caen (FR) , Inhabitants 2021: 152577
Total green area (Ha) 332.01
Total green quiet area: 44.27 (Ha); 13.33 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 14401; 9.2 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 332.01 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.29 (Ha)

Castelló de la Plana

Green quiet areas in Castelló de la Plana urban centre

Castelló de la Plana (ES) , Inhabitants 2021: 145839
Total green area (Ha) 74.47
Total green quiet area: 36.17 (Ha); 48.57 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 55609; 37.9 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 74.47 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.18 (Ha)

Charleroi

Green quiet areas in Charleroi urban centre

Charleroi (BE) , Inhabitants 2021: 208739
Total green area (Ha) 715.6
Total green quiet area: 453.05 (Ha); 63.31 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 34114; 19.61 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 987.74 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 272.14 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.13 (Ha)

Chemnitz

Green quiet areas in Chemnitz urban centre

Chemnitz (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 163402
Total green area (Ha) 466.51
Total green quiet area: 189.6 (Ha); 40.64 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 51212; 32.98 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 554.15 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 87.64 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.24 (Ha)

Clermont-Ferrand

Green quiet areas in Clermont-Ferrand urban centre

Clermont-Ferrand (FR) , Inhabitants 2021: 194147
Total green area (Ha) 473.8
Total green quiet area: 392.75 (Ha); 82.89 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 60790; 32.04 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 473.8 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.28 (Ha)

Cork

Green quiet areas in Cork urban centre

Cork (IE) , Inhabitants 2021: 160801
Total green area (Ha) 341.84
Total green quiet area: 146.75 (Ha); 42.93 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 26070; 16.11 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 341.84 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.15 (Ha)

Częstochowa

Green quiet areas in Częstochowa urban centre

Częstochowa (PL) , Inhabitants 2021: 160543
Total green area (Ha) 235.27
Total green quiet area: 90.74 (Ha); 38.57 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 20063; 11.07 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 235.27 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.98 (Ha)

Darmstadt

Green quiet areas in Darmstadt urban centre

Darmstadt (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 125108
Total green area (Ha) 649.33
Total green quiet area: 198.85 (Ha); 30.62 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 44608; 35.83 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 668.38 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 19.05 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.75 (Ha)

Den Haag

Green quiet areas in Den Haag urban centre

0 5 km

Quiet green Non quiet green and forest
Quiet forests Urban centre

Den Haag (NL) , Inhabitants 2021: 829920
Total green area (Ha) 1951.98
Total green quiet area: 1056.45 (Ha); 54.12 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 375013; 46.14 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 1951.98 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.03 (Ha)

Dresden

Green quiet areas in Dresden urban centre

Dresden (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 497265
Total green area (Ha) 1088.83
Total green quiet area: 623.99 (Ha); 57.31 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 121850; 26.04 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 1165 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 76.17 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.36 (Ha)

Dublin

Green quiet areas in Dublin urban centre

0 5 km

- | | | | |
|---|---------------|---|----------------------------|
| | Non quiet green and forest |
| | Urban centre |

Dublin (IE) , Inhabitants 2021: 1202305
Total green area (Ha) 3583.76
Total green quiet area: 1829.2 (Ha); 51.04 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 357505; 31.47 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 3593.16 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 9.4 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.67 (Ha)

Dunkerque

Green quiet areas in Dunkerque urban centre

Dunkerque (FR) , Inhabitants 2021: 133652
Total green area (Ha) 125.07
Total green quiet area: 30.06 (Ha); 24.03 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 21761; 16.87 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 125.07 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 0.94 (Ha)

Düsseldorf

Green quiet areas in Düsseldorf urban centre

Düsseldorf (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 567442

Total green area (Ha) 1457.77

Total green quiet area: 433.61 (Ha); 29.74 (%)

People with acces to green quiet area 59327; 11.91 (%)

Green area in Urban centre 1820.06 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 362.29 (Ha)

Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 4.37 (Ha)

Eindhoven

Green quiet areas in Eindhoven urban centre

Eindhoven (NL) , Inhabitants 2021: 269318
Total green area (Ha) 983.18
Total green quiet area: 545.86 (Ha); 55.52 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 124494; 46.64 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 997.69 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 14.51 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.92 (Ha)

Elbląg

Green quiet areas in Elbląg urban centre

Elbląg (PL) , Inhabitants 2021: 99253

Total green area (Ha) 143.86

Total green quiet area: 70.6 (Ha); 49.08 (%)

People with acces to green quiet area 19084; 16.89 (%)

Green area in Urban centre 144.42 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0.56 (Ha)

Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.09 (Ha)

Enschede

Green quiet areas in Enschede urban centre

Enschede (NL) , Inhabitants 2021: 123926
Total green area (Ha) 363.3
Total green quiet area: 222.71 (Ha); 61.3 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 54304; 43.09 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 363.3 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.93 (Ha)

Erlangen

Green quiet areas in Erlangen urban centre

Erlangen (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 100546
Total green area (Ha) 334.81
Total green quiet area: 105.54 (Ha); 31.52 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 23926; 26.42 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 510.8 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 175.99 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.65 (Ha)

Frankfurt am Main

Green quiet areas in Frankfurt am Main urban centre

Frankfurt am Main (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 914744
Total green area (Ha) 1969.14
Total green quiet area: 329.93 (Ha); 16.76 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 229018; 27.36 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 2118.78 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 149.64 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.39 (Ha)

Breisgau

Green quiet areas in Freiburg im Breisgau urban centre

Freiburg im Breisgau (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 205837
Total green area (Ha) 593.03
Total green quiet area: 363.13 (Ha); 61.23 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 69565; 36.63 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 643.21 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 50.18 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.06 (Ha)

Fuenlabrada

Green quiet areas in Fuenlabrada urban centre

Fuenlabrada (ES) , Inhabitants 2021: 192621
Total green area (Ha) 214.87
Total green quiet area: 43.6 (Ha); 20.29 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 94133; 47.19 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 218.72 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 3.85 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.06 (Ha)

Fürth

Green quiet areas in Fürth urban centre

Fürth (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 569927

Total green area (Ha) 1255.1

Total green quiet area: 585.43 (Ha); 46.64 (%)

People with acces to green quiet area 184508; 34.73 (%)

Green area in Urban centre 1708.89 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 453.79 (Ha)

Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.47 (Ha)

Gdansk

Green quiet areas in Gdańsk urban centre

0 5 km

Gdańsk (PL) , Inhabitants 2021: 449978

Total green area (Ha) 1733.7

Total green quiet area: 1234.89 (Ha); 71.23 (%)

People with acces to green quiet area 194598; 47.61 (%)

Green area in Urban centre 1858.83 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 125.13 (Ha)

Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 7.99 (Ha)

Gdynia

Green quiet areas in Gdynia urban centre

Gdynia (PL) , Inhabitants 2021: 125048

Total green area (Ha) 979.71

Total green quiet area: 850.9 (Ha); 86.85 (%)

People with acces to green quiet area 62962; 43.74 (%)

Green area in Urban centre 979.71 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)

Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 52.86 (Ha)

Genève

Green quiet areas in Genève urban centre

FOEN / Swiss Parks Network, swisstopo, Esri, TomTom, Garmin, Foursquare, GeoTechnologies, Inc, METI/NASA, USGS

0 5 km

	Non quiet green and forest		
	Urban centre		

Genève (CH-FR) , Inhabitants 2021: 465626
Total green area (Ha) 548.14
Total green quiet area: 328.72 (Ha); 59.97 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 136748; 34.22 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 548.16 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0.02 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.7 (Ha)

Gent

Green quiet areas in Gent urban centre

Gent (BE) , Inhabitants 2021: 239153
Total green area (Ha) 331.12
Total green quiet area: 133.03 (Ha); 40.18 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 46135; 19.99 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 379.74 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 48.62 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.86 (Ha)

Gijón

Green quiet areas in Gijón urban centre

Gijón (ES) , Inhabitants 2021: 246713

Total green area (Ha) 180.3

Total green quiet area: 101.09 (Ha); 56.07 (%)

People with acces to green quiet area 151362; 61.06 (%)

Green area in Urban centre 183.05 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 2.75 (Ha)

Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.3 (Ha)

Górnośląski Związek Met.

Green quiet areas in Górnośląski Związek Met. urban centre

0 5 km

	Non quiet green and forest		
	Urban centre		

Górnośląski Związek Met. (PL) , Inhabitants 2021: 1079187

Total green area (Ha) 4796.93

Total green quiet area: 3256.31 (Ha); 67.88 (%)

People with acces to green quiet area 515053; 49.76 (%)

Green area in Urban centre 5678.39 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 881.46 (Ha)

Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.93 (Ha)

Gorzów Wielkopolski

Green quiet areas in Gorzów Wielkopolski urban centre

- | | |
|---|--|
| Non quiet green and forest |
| Urban centre |

Gorzów Wielkopolski (PL) , Inhabitants 2021: 99943
Total green area (Ha) 312.59
Total green quiet area: 187.89 (Ha); 60.11 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 45096; 41.32 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 312.59 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.74 (Ha)

Göteborg

Green quiet areas in Göteborg urban centre

Göteborg (SE) , Inhabitants 2021: 552807

Total green area (Ha) 3884.67

Total green quiet area: 2311.12 (Ha); 59.49 (%)

People with acces to green quiet area 299022; 63.93 (%)

Green area in Urban centre 4860.27 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 975.6 (Ha)

Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 9.07 (Ha)

Göttingen

Green quiet areas in Göttingen urban centre

Göttingen (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 94661
Total green area (Ha) 391.93
Total green quiet area: 279.47 (Ha); 71.31 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 28860; 30.25 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 411.16 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 19.23 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.42 (Ha)

Gouda

Green quiet areas in Gouda urban centre

Gouda (NL) , Inhabitants 2021: 76757
Total green area (Ha) 102.48
Total green quiet area: 41.61 (Ha); 40.6 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 32380; 47.48 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 102.49 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0.01 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.14 (Ha)

Graz

Green quiet areas in Graz urban centre

Graz (AT) , Inhabitants 2021: 259678
Total green area (Ha) 654.85
Total green quiet area: 471.19 (Ha); 71.95 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 66264; 25.12 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 656.86 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 2.01 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.75 (Ha)

Grenoble

Green quiet areas in Grenoble urban centre

Grenoble (FR) , Inhabitants 2021: 321629
Total green area (Ha) 892.78
Total green quiet area: 442.63 (Ha); 49.58 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 71568; 22.04 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 902.26 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 9.48 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.29 (Ha)

Groningen

Green quiet areas in Groningen urban centre

Groningen (NL), Inhabitants 2021: 186767
Total green area (Ha) 535.97
Total green quiet area: 303.67 (Ha); 56.66 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 110877; 59.11 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 554.11 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 18.14 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.54 (Ha)

Gröpelingen / Vegesack

Green quiet areas in Gröpelingen / Vegesack urban centre

Gröpelingen / Vegesack (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 74927
Total green area (Ha) 317.51
Total green quiet area: 163.94 (Ha); 51.63 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 15946; 23.26 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 392.2 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 74.69 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.99 (Ha)

Haarlem

Green quiet areas in Haarlem urban centre

Haarlem (NL) , Inhabitants 2021: 218496
Total green area (Ha) 512.27
Total green quiet area: 298.15 (Ha); 58.2 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 75161; 33.98 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 512.27 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.12 (Ha)

Halle an der Saale

Green quiet areas in Halle an der Saale urban centre

Halle an der Saale (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 200656
Total green area (Ha) 816.87
Total green quiet area: 389.53 (Ha); 47.69 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 63821; 31.08 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 816.87 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.22 (Ha)

Hamburg

Green quiet areas in Hamburg urban centre

0 5 km

Hamburg (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 1696739

Total green area (Ha) 4814.42

Total green quiet area: 3272.37 (Ha); 67.97 (%)

People with acces to green quiet area 506846; 32.81 (%)

Green area in Urban centre 5552.59 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 738.17 (Ha)

Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 6.79 (Ha)

Hanau

Green quiet areas in Hanau urban centre

Hanau (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 81214
Total green area (Ha) 270.52
Total green quiet area: 53.14 (Ha); 19.64 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 21572; 24.91 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 278.42 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 7.9 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1 (Ha)

Hannover

Green quiet areas in Hannover urban centre

0 5 km

	Non quiet green and forest		
	Urban centre		

Hannover (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 560886

Total green area (Ha) 2495.93

Total green quiet area: 997.28 (Ha); 39.96 (%)

People with acces to green quiet area 160601; 30.66 (%)

Green area in Urban centre 2603.51 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 107.58 (Ha)

Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.33 (Ha)

Harburg

Green quiet areas in Harburg urban centre

Harburg (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 99307

Total green area (Ha) 307.74

Total green quiet area: 185.14 (Ha); 60.16 (%)

People with acces to green quiet area 32385; 32.53 (%)

Green area in Urban centre 307.74 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)

Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 6.61 (Ha)

Havirov

Green quiet areas in Haviřov urban centre

Haviřov (CZ) , Inhabitants 2021: 62676

Total green area (Ha) 278.04

Total green quiet area: 202.75 (Ha); 72.92 (%)

People with acces to green quiet area 25744; 37.37 (%)

Green area in Urban centre 294.66 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 16.62 (Ha)

Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 0.36 (Ha)

Heidelberg

Green quiet areas in Heidelberg urban centre

Heidelberg (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 128552
Total green area (Ha) 630.05
Total green quiet area: 519.19 (Ha); 82.4 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 36989; 27.58 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 630.16 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0.11 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 23.82 (Ha)

Heilbronn

Green quiet areas in Heilbronn urban centre

Heilbronn (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 97074
Total green area (Ha) 114.79
Total green quiet area: 88.28 (Ha); 76.91 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 22269; 23.72 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 122.19 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 7.4 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 4.14 (Ha)

Helmond

Green quiet areas in Helmond urban centre

Helmond (NL) , Inhabitants 2021: 90148
Total green area (Ha) 422.83
Total green quiet area: 300.3 (Ha); 71.02 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 49805; 54.03 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 444.98 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 22.15 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 6.86 (Ha)

Helsingborg

Green quiet areas in Helsingborg urban centre

Helsingborg (SE) , Inhabitants 2021: 103729
Total green area (Ha) 359.28
Total green quiet area: 48.41 (Ha); 13.47 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 21325; 21.32 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 359.28 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.41 (Ha)

Helsinki

Green quiet areas in Helsinki urban centre

0 5 km

Non quiet green and forest	
Urban centre	

Helsinki (FI), Inhabitants 2021: 1008991
Total green area (Ha) 8727.79
Total green quiet area: 5350.88 (Ha); 61.31 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 965702; 95.11 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 8728.36 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0.57 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.65 (Ha)

Hengelo

Green quiet areas in Hengelo urban centre

Hengelo (NL) , Inhabitants 2021: 72962
Total green area (Ha) 194.04
Total green quiet area: 131.01 (Ha); 67.52 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 37639; 50.21 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 197.52 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 3.48 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.69 (Ha)

Hildesheim

Green quiet areas in Hildesheim urban centre

Hildesheim (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 63482
Total green area (Ha) 146.56
Total green quiet area: 59.9 (Ha); 40.87 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 62768; 30.61 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 146.56 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.77 (Ha)

Hilversum

Green quiet areas in Hilversum urban centre

Hilversum (NL) , Inhabitants 2021: 87394
Total green area (Ha) 275.04
Total green quiet area: 194.9 (Ha); 70.86 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 26413; 31.76 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 297.52 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 22.48 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 4.39 (Ha)

Hrabuvka

Green quiet areas in Hrabuvka urban centre

Hrabuvka (CZ) , Inhabitants 2021: 104306
Total green area (Ha) 279.3
Total green quiet area: 103.41 (Ha); 37.02 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 34073; 32.06 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 424 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 144.7 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 0.69 (Ha)

Ingolstadt

Green quiet areas in Ingolstadt urban centre

Ingolstadt (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 104914
Total green area (Ha) 265.84
Total green quiet area: 95.66 (Ha); 35.98 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 12570; 11.77 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 267.77 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 1.93 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.46 (Ha)

Innsbruck

Green quiet areas in Innsbruck urban centre

Innsbruck (AT) , Inhabitants 2021: 124327
Total green area (Ha) 279.73
Total green quiet area: 138.97 (Ha); 49.68 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 43371; 33.44 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 285.4 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 5.67 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.13 (Ha)

Jönköping / Huskvarna

Green quiet areas in Jönköping / Huskvarna urban centre

Jönköping / Huskvarna (SE) , Inhabitants 2021: 68683
Total green area (Ha) 528.42
Total green quiet area: 354.01 (Ha); 66.99 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 28996; 41.14 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 528.42 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 10.17 (Ha)

Jyväskylä

Green quiet areas in Jyväskylä urban centre

Jyväskylä (FI) , Inhabitants 2021: 60317
Total green area (Ha) 603.42
Total green quiet area: 369.46 (Ha); 61.23 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 29175; 45.32 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 603.42 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 5.46 (Ha)

Karlsruhe

Green quiet areas in Karlsruhe urban centre

Karlsruhe (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 243900
Total green area (Ha) 1491.19
Total green quiet area: 683.06 (Ha); 45.81 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 89362; 35.73 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 1511.88 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 20.69 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.73 (Ha)

Kassel

Green quiet areas in Kassel urban centre

Kassel (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 204272
Total green area (Ha) 655.54
Total green quiet area: 365.28 (Ha); 55.72 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 40958; 23.48 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 789.47 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 133.93 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 5.66 (Ha)

Kasztelanka

Green quiet areas in Kasztelanka urban centre

Kasztelanka (PL) , Inhabitants 2021: 59076
Total green area (Ha) 100.95
Total green quiet area: 35.67 (Ha); 35.33 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 15150; 22.52 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 102.35 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 1.4 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.11 (Ha)

Kaunas

Green quiet areas in Kaunas urban centre

Kaunas (LT) , Inhabitants 2021: 235793
Total green area (Ha) 975.54
Total green quiet area: 670.02 (Ha); 68.68 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 78164; 32.83 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 975.93 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0.39 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.8 (Ha)

Kiel

Green quiet areas in Kiel urban centre

Kiel (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 219484
Total green area (Ha) 648,64
Total green quiet area: 261.42 (Ha); 40.3 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 57965; 28.26 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 814.23 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 165.59 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.51 (Ha)

Kielce

Green quiet areas in Kielce urban centre

Kielce (PL) , Inhabitants 2021: 146889
Total green area (Ha) 263.01
Total green quiet area: 213.63 (Ha); 81.23 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 30456; 18.27 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 263.01 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 4.3 (Ha)

København

Green quiet areas in København urban centre

0 5 km

Non quiet green and forest	
Urban centre	

København (DK) , Inhabitants 2021: 1360930
Total green area (Ha) 3037.25
Total green quiet area: 1620.82 (Ha); 53.36 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 278647; 29.88 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 3344.86 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 307.61 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 4.81 (Ha)

Koblenz

Green quiet areas in Koblenz urban centre

Koblenz (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 113157
Total green area (Ha) 679.58
Total green quiet area: 428.49 (Ha); 63.05 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 33991; 34.24 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 761.07 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 81.49 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.59 (Ha)

Köln

Green quiet areas in Köln urban centre

0 5 km

Quiet green
Quiet forests
Non quiet green and forest
Urban centre

Köln (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 968046
Total green area (Ha) 4850.82
Total green quiet area: 2087.03 (Ha); 43.02 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 228603; 23.21 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 4908.21 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 57.39 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 6.57 (Ha)

Kraków

Green quiet areas in Kraków urban centre

0 5 km

Kraków (PL) , Inhabitants 2021: 706924
Total green area (Ha) 1609.48
Total green quiet area: 844.87 (Ha); 52.49 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 342696; 48.72 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 1612.14 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 2.66 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.91 (Ha)

Krefeld

Green quiet areas in Krefeld urban centre

Krefeld (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 176887
Total green area (Ha) 381.24
Total green quiet area: 258.72 (Ha); 67.86 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 37736; 23.67 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 381.24 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.98 (Ha)

Lahti

Green quiet areas in Lahti urban centre

Lahti (FI) , Inhabitants 2021: 55187
Total green area (Ha) 574.28
Total green quiet area: 432.49 (Ha); 75.31 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 28755; 48.83 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 574.28 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 5.1 (Ha)

Lausanne

Green quiet areas in Lausanne urban centre

Lausanne (CH) , Inhabitants 2021: 287814
Total green area (Ha) 746,46
Total green quiet area: 392.65 (Ha); 52.6 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 97150; 34.01 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 747.23 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0.77 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.76 (Ha)

Lefkosia

Green quiet areas in Lefkosia urban centre

Lefkosia (CY) , Inhabitants 2021: 215838
Total green area (Ha) 217.94
Total green quiet area: 32.1 (Ha); 14.73 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 10523; 5.01 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 255.75 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 37.81 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 0.66 (Ha)

Leiden

Green quiet areas in Leiden urban centre

Leiden (NL) , Inhabitants 2021: 268792
Total green area (Ha) 419.4
Total green quiet area: 239.42 (Ha); 57.09 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 130853; 49.85 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 454.29 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 34.89 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.06 (Ha)

Leipzig

Green quiet areas in Leipzig urban centre

Leipzig (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 554941

Total green area (Ha) 2494.91

Total green quiet area: 1423.07 (Ha); 57.04 (%)

People with acces to green quiet area 207760; 40.43 (%)

Green area in Urban centre 2656.96 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 162.05 (Ha)

Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.97 (Ha)

Lemesos

Green quiet areas in Lemesos urban centre

Lemesos (CY), Inhabitants 2021: 162983
Total green area (Ha) 81.6
Total green quiet area: 18.24 (Ha); 22.35 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 5968; 3.84 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 83.37 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 1.77 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.17 (Ha)

Lens

Green quiet areas in Lens urban centre

Lens (FR) , Inhabitants 2021: 162483
Total green area (Ha) 443.15
Total green quiet area: 177.04 (Ha); 39.95 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 30042; 23.1 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 443.15 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.54 (Ha)

León

Green quiet areas in León urban centre

León (ES) , Inhabitants 2021: 154254
Total green area (Ha) 103.23
Total green quiet area: 37.65 (Ha); 36.47 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 80838; 64.12 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 114.72 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 11.49 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 0.25 (Ha)

Les Clayes-sous-Bois

Green quiet areas in Les Clayes-sous-Bois urban centre

Les Clayes-sous-Bois (FR) , Inhabitants 2021: 52165
Total green area (Ha) 179.48
Total green quiet area: 151.38 (Ha); 84.34 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 15391; 28.32 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 179.48 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 5.23 (Ha)

Leuven

Green quiet areas in Leuven urban centre

Leuven (BE) , Inhabitants 2021: 77260
Total green area (Ha) 204.95
Total green quiet area: 140.39 (Ha); 68.5 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 15621; 19.24 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 219.11 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 14.16 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.25 (Ha)

Liberec

Green quiet areas in Liberec urban centre

Liberec (CZ) , Inhabitants 2021: 92381
Total green area (Ha) 547.12
Total green quiet area: 352.04 (Ha); 64.34 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 43981; 46.56 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 563.22 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 16.1 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.7 (Ha)

Liège

Green quiet areas in Liège urban centre

Liège (BE) , Inhabitants 2021: 366369
Total green area (Ha) 661.31
Total green quiet area: 414.08 (Ha); 62.62 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 40577; 21.39 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 1579.02 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 917.71 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 6.35 (Ha)

Limerick

Green quiet areas in Limerick urban centre

Limerick (IE) , Inhabitants 2021: 87826
Total green area (Ha) 58.38
Total green quiet area: 40.96 (Ha); 70.16 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 6689; 7.48 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 58.38 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.84 (Ha)

Limoges

Green quiet areas in Limoges urban centre

Limoges (FR) , Inhabitants 2021: 116676
Total green area (Ha) 252.57
Total green quiet area: 111.87 (Ha); 44.29 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 12156; 10.07 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 252.57 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.47 (Ha)

Linköping

Green quiet areas in Linköping urban centre

Linköping (SE) , Inhabitants 2021: 98073
Total green area (Ha) 675.85
Total green quiet area: 547.43 (Ha); 81 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 69985; 71.45 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 675.85 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 6.85 (Ha)

Linz

Green quiet areas in Linz urban centre

Linz (AT) , Inhabitants 2021: 208671
Total green area (Ha) 604.48
Total green quiet area: 379.14 (Ha); 62.72 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 78260; 37.09 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 604.59 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0.11 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.74 (Ha)

Lódzk

Green quiet areas in Łódź urban centre

0 5 km

Non quiet green and forest	
Urban centre	

Łódź (PL) , Inhabitants 2021: 601217
Total green area (Ha) 1679.32
Total green quiet area: 955.51 (Ha); 56.9 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 6781; 33.67 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 1682.42 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 3.1 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 4 (Ha)

Logroño

Green quiet areas in Logroño urban centre

Logroño (ES) , Inhabitants 2021: 147234
Total green area (Ha) 177.26
Total green quiet area: 12.49 (Ha); 7.05 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 24557; 16.49 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 177.77 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0.51 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 0.22 (Ha)

Lübeck

Green quiet areas in Lübeck urban centre

Lübeck (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 186031
Total green area (Ha) 362.59
Total green quiet area: 161.18 (Ha); 44.45 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 20013; 12.28 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 472.03 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 109.44 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.28 (Ha)

Lublin

Green quiet areas in Lublin urban centre

Lublin (PL) , Inhabitants 2021: 294675
Total green area (Ha) 820.74
Total green quiet area: 554.92 (Ha); 67.61 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 98405; 31.77 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 831.36 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 10.62 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.53 (Ha)

Lugano

Green quiet areas in Lugano urban centre

Lugano (CH) , Inhabitants 2021: 73220
Total green area (Ha) 377.37
Total green quiet area: 248.77 (Ha); 65.92 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 27385; 36.28 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 377.37 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.32 (Ha)

Lund

Green quiet areas in Lund urban centre

Lund (SE) , Inhabitants 2021: 90448
Total green area (Ha) 439.26
Total green quiet area: 234.46 (Ha); 53.38 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 60982; 68.11 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 441.34 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 2.08 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.4 (Ha)

Lütten Klein

Green quiet areas in Lütten Klein urban centre

Lütten Klein (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 64976
Total green area (Ha) 132.4
Total green quiet area: 47.9 (Ha); 36.18 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 22202; 32.56 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 132.41 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0.01 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.87 (Ha)

Luxembourg

Green quiet areas in Luxembourg urban centre

Luxembourg (LU) , Inhabitants 2021: 157407
Total green area (Ha) 684.89
Total green quiet area: 204.08 (Ha); 29.8 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 38353; 26.45 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 684.89 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 0.95 (Ha)

Lyon

Green quiet areas in Lyon urban centre

0 5 km

Lyon (FR) , Inhabitants 2021: 1131936
Total green area (Ha) 1999.18
Total green quiet area: 882.95 (Ha); 44.17 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 258064; 23.17 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 2001.41 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 2.23 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.07 (Ha)

Madrid

Green quiet areas in Madrid urban centre

0 5 km

	Non quiet green and forest		
	Urban centre		

Madrid (ES) , Inhabitants 2021: 4150910

Total green area (Ha) 5170.74

Total green quiet area: 1617.71 (Ha); 31.29 (%)

People with acces to green quiet area 1207359; 33.01 (%)

Green area in Urban centre 5652.86 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 482.12 (Ha)

Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.09 (Ha)

Magdeburg

Green quiet areas in Magdeburg urban centre

GeoBasis-DE / LGB, GeoBasis-DE / LVermGeo LSA, Esri, TomTom, Garmin, Foursquare, GeoTechnologies, Inc, METI/NASA, USGS

Magdeburg (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 206172

Total green area (Ha) 664.26

Total green quiet area: 291.23 (Ha); 43.84 (%)

People with acces to green quiet area 39675; 24.06 (%)

Green area in Urban centre 664.26 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)

Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.39 (Ha)

Mainz

Green quiet areas in Mainz urban centre

Mainz (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 209211
Total green area (Ha) 390.25
Total green quiet area: 121.55 (Ha); 31.15 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 63750; 32.14 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 390.25 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 0.99 (Ha)

Malmö

Green quiet areas in Malmö urban centre

Malmö (SE) , Inhabitants 2021: 321385
Total green area (Ha) 745.37
Total green quiet area: 186.48 (Ha); 25.02 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 131711; 43.93 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 745.37 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.02 (Ha)

Mannheim/Ludwigshafen

Green quiet areas in Mannheim/Ludwigshafen urban centre

0 5 km

 Non quiet green and forest
 Urban centre

Mannheim/Ludwigshafen (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 435036
Total green area (Ha) 772.15
Total green quiet area: 371.89 (Ha); 48.16 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 95119; 24.17 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 844.61 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 72.46 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 7.12 (Ha)

Mantes en Yvelines

Green quiet areas in Mantés en Yvelines urban centre

Mantes en Yvelines (FR) , Inhabitants 2021: 85264
Total green area (Ha) 230.4
Total green quiet area: 162.68 (Ha); 70.61 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 25543; 29.49 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 230.4 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.62 (Ha)

Marseille

Green quiet areas in Marseille urban centre

Marseille (FR) , Inhabitants 2021: 882996
Total green area (Ha) 1371.01
Total green quiet area: 893.05 (Ha); 65.14 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 207583; 23.84 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 1371.08 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0.07 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.69 (Ha)

Martigues / Port-de-Bouc

Green quiet areas in Martigues / Port-de-Bouc urban centre

Martigues / Port-de-Bouc (FR) , Inhabitants 2021: 50911
Total green area (Ha) 182.12
Total green quiet area: 106.96 (Ha); 58.73 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 9479; 18.21 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 182.86 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0.74 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 4.2 (Ha)

Maurepas / Montigny-le-Bretonneux

Green quiet areas in Maurepas / Montigny-le-Bretonneux urban centre

Maurepas / Montigny-le-Bretonneux (FR) , Inhabitants 2021: 152689
Total green area (Ha) 596.78
Total green quiet area: 307.46 (Ha); 51.52 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 54028; 34.87 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 622.74 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 25.96 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 6.65 (Ha)

Moers / Rheinhausen

Green quiet areas in Moers / Rheinhausen urban centre

Moers / Rheinhausen (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 182029
Total green area (Ha) 815.02
Total green quiet area: 421.47 (Ha); 51.71 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 62768; 33.35 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 815.02 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 6.01 (Ha)

Mönchengladbach

Green quiet areas in Mönchengladbach urban centre

Mönchengladbach (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 200219
Total green area (Ha) 523.97
Total green quiet area: 356.48 (Ha); 68.03 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 47889; 23.54 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 524.55 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0.58 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.86 (Ha)

München

Green quiet areas in München urban centre

0 5 km

	Non quiet green and forest		
	Urban centre		

München (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 1644454
Total green area (Ha) 3565
Total green quiet area: 1573.12 (Ha); 44.13 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 479496; 33.46 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 5230.78 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 1665.78 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3 (Ha)

Münster

Green quiet areas in Münster urban centre

Münster (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 198759
Total green area (Ha) 633.26
Total green quiet area: 389.3 (Ha); 61.48 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 61944; 31.13 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 633.26 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.55 (Ha)

Nantes

Green quiet areas in Nantes urban centre

Nantes (FR) , Inhabitants 2021: 448172
Total green area (Ha) 1035.66
Total green quiet area: 554.22 (Ha); 53.51 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 135294; 31.71 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 1035.66 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.18 (Ha)

Neu Wulmstorf / N.Fischbek / Hausbruch

Green quiet areas in Neu Wulmstorf / N.Fischbek / Hausbruch urban centre

Neu Wulmstorf / N.Fischbek / Hausbruch (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 59020
Total green area (Ha) 168.7
Total green quiet area: 134.87 (Ha); 79.95 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 15859; 35.05 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 261.41 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 92.71 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.15 (Ha)

Nice

Green quiet areas in Nice urban centre

0 5 km

Non quiet green and forest	
Urban centre	

Nice (FR) , Inhabitants 2021: 438927
Total green area (Ha) 1021.58
Total green quiet area: 856.35 (Ha); 83.83 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 26416; 6.31 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 1115.22 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 93.64 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.51 (Ha)

Nieuwegein / Usselstein

Green quiet areas in Nieuwegein / IJsselstein urban centre

Nieuwegein / IJsselstein (NL) , Inhabitants 2021: 108500
Total green area (Ha) 338.95
Total green quiet area: 160.69 (Ha); 47.41 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 50499; 46.68 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 398.33 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 59.38 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.53 (Ha)

Nijmegen

Green quiet areas in Nijmegen urban centre

Nijmegen (NL) , Inhabitants 2021: 167532
Total green area (Ha) 476.27
Total green quiet area: 248.4 (Ha); 52.16 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 87010; 50.76 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 477.67 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 1.4 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.32 (Ha)

Norrköping

Green quiet areas in Norrköping urban centre

Norrköping (SE) , Inhabitants 2021: 89963
Total green area (Ha) 464.6
Total green quiet area: 266.38 (Ha); 57.34 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 50013; 54 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 464.6 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 5.26 (Ha)

Odense

Green quiet areas in Odense urban centre

Odense (DK) , Inhabitants 2021: 135431

Total green area (Ha) 503.35

Total green quiet area: 388.4 (Ha); 77.16 (%)

People with acces to green quiet area 58640; 44.31 (%)

Green area in Urban centre 645.26 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 141.91 (Ha)

Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.78 (Ha)

Oldenburg

Green quiet areas in Oldenburg (Oldenburg) urban centre

Oldenburg (Oldenburg) (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 165521
Total green area (Ha) 582.62
Total green quiet area: 134.54 (Ha); 23.09 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area: 16548; 10.27 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 600.7 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 18.08 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.19 (Ha)

Olomouc

Green quiet areas in Olomouc urban centre

Olomouc (CZ) , Inhabitants 2021: 82946
Total green area (Ha) 107.06
Total green quiet area: 56.25 (Ha); 52.54 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 25008; 31.09 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 107.06 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.41 (Ha)

Olsztyn

Green quiet areas in Olsztyn urban centre

Olsztyn (PL) , Inhabitants 2021: 148217
Total green area (Ha) 500.25
Total green quiet area: 436 (Ha); 87.16 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 59444; 38.05 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 514.38 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 14.13 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 6.69 (Ha)

Opole

Green quiet areas in Opole urban centre

Opole (PL) , Inhabitants 2021: 86543
Total green area (Ha) 98.02
Total green quiet area: 62.72 (Ha); 63.99 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 18406; 19.59 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 105.51 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 7.49 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.94 (Ha)

Örebro

Green quiet areas in Örebro urban centre

Örebro (SE) , Inhabitants 2021: 92695
Total green area (Ha) 569.89
Total green quiet area: 139.15 (Ha); 24.42 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 20346; 21.02 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 569.89 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.58 (Ha)

Oslo

Green quiet areas in Oslo urban centre

Oslo (NO) , Inhabitants 2021: 940449

Total green area (Ha) 5368.66

Total green quiet area: 4416.8 (Ha); 82.27 (%)

People with acces to green quiet area 337794; 37.72 (%)

Green area in Urban centre 5512.04 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 143.38 (Ha)

Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 24.73 (Ha)

Osnabrück

Green quiet areas in Osnabrück urban centre

Osnabrück (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 122803

Total green area (Ha) 510.93

Total green quiet area: 349.79 (Ha); 68.46 (%)

People with acces to green quiet area 29544; 24.1 (%)

Green area in Urban centre 512.66 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 1.73 (Ha)

Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 5.22 (Ha)

Ostrava

Green quiet areas in Ostrava urban centre

Ostrava (CZ) , Inhabitants 2021: 54301

Total green area (Ha) 199.72

Total green quiet area: 42.11 (Ha); 21.08 (%)

People with acces to green quiet area 10968; 19.42 (%)

Green area in Urban centre 199.72 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)

Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.28 (Ha)

Oulu / Uleåborg

Green quiet areas in Oulu / Uleåborg urban centre

Oulu / Uleåborg (FI) , Inhabitants 2021: 74510
Total green area (Ha) 715.95
Total green quiet area: 340.85 (Ha); 47.61 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 38825; 50.62 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 715.95 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.37 (Ha)

Oviedo

Green quiet areas in Oviedo urban centre

Oviedo (ES) , Inhabitants 2021: 201559
Total green area (Ha) 227.09
Total green quiet area: 160.01 (Ha); 70.46 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 94307; 45.97 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 238.07 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 10.98 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.12 (Ha)

Pamplona/Iruna

Green quiet areas in Pamplona/Iruña urban centre

0 5 km

Non quiet green and forest	
Urban centre	

Pamplona/Iruña (ES) , Inhabitants 2021: 335129
Total green area (Ha) 562.17
Total green quiet area: 180.09 (Ha); 32.03 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 163654; 50 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 568.87 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 6.7 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 0.97 (Ha)

Paris

Green quiet areas in Paris urban centre

0 5 10 km
|-----|-----|-----|

	Non quiet green and forest		
	Urban centre		

Paris (FR) , Inhabitants 2021: 9586886

Total green area (Ha) 21018.83

Total green quiet area: 11799.19 (Ha); 56.14 (%)

People with acces to green quiet area 2326538; 24.16 (%)

Green area in Urban centre 21320.82 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 301.99 (Ha)

Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.23 (Ha)

Pforzheim

Green quiet areas in Pforzheim urban centre

Pforzheim (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 95009
Total green area (Ha) 415.54
Total green quiet area: 199.46 (Ha); 48 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 23930; 25.03 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 415.54 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 4.5 (Ha)

Pijnacker / Berkel en Rodenrijs

Green quiet areas in Pijnacker / Berkel en Rodenrijs urban centre

Pijnacker / Berkel en Rodenrijs (NL) , Inhabitants 2021: 72259
Total green area (Ha) 62.79
Total green quiet area: 33.37 (Ha); 53.15 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 12622; 52.91 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 183.54 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 120.75 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 26.54 (Ha)

Plock

Green quiet areas in Plock urban centre

Plock (PL) , Inhabitants 2021: 68079
Total green area (Ha) 193.59
Total green quiet area: 136.77 (Ha); 70.65 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 33153; 42.13 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 193.59 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 0.81 (Ha)

Plzeň

Green quiet areas in Plzeň urban centre

Plzeň (CZ) , Inhabitants 2021: 97660

Total green area (Ha) 161.41

Total green quiet area: 88.15 (Ha); 54.61 (%)

People with acces to green quiet area 27122; 26.97 (%)

Green area in Urban centre 161.41 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)

Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.74 (Ha)

Poissy

Green quiet areas in Poissy urban centre

Poissy (FR) , Inhabitants 2021: 82078
Total green area (Ha) 277.35
Total green quiet area: 161.47 (Ha); 58.22 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 20275; 23.7 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 277.35 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 7.18 (Ha)

Porto

Green quiet areas in Porto urban centre

Porto (PT) , Inhabitants 2021: 863931
Total green area (Ha) 573.29
Total green quiet area: 381.26 (Ha); 66.5 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 110450; 30.71 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 3025.16 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 2451.87 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.69 (Ha)

Porz

Green quiet areas in Porz urban centre

Land NRW, LVermGeo RP, Kadaster, Esri, TomTom, Garmin, Foursquare, GeoTechnologies, Inc, METI/NASA, USGS

Porz (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 102058

Total green area (Ha) 361.42

Total green quiet area: 233.54 (Ha); 64.62 (%)

People with acces to green quiet area 16394; 15.37 (%)

Green area in Urban centre 361.42 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)

Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.87 (Ha)

Potsdam

Green quiet areas in Potsdam urban centre

- | | |
|---|--|
| Non quiet green and forest |
| Urban centre |

Potsdam (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 147377
Total green area (Ha) 738.82
Total green quiet area: 371.43 (Ha); 50.27 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 35722; 24.35 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 754.1 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 15.28 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 4.44 (Ha)

Poznan

Green quiet areas in Poznań urban centre

Poznań (PL) , Inhabitants 2021: 535302
Total green area (Ha) 2066.86
Total green quiet area: 1356.71 (Ha); 65.64 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 149199; 29.95 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 2131.99 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 65.13 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 6.33 (Ha)

Praha

Green quiet areas in Praha urban centre

0 5 km

Quiet green
Quiet forests
Non quiet green and forest
Urban centre

Praha (CZ) , Inhabitants 2021: 1151091
Total green area (Ha) 5146.79
Total green quiet area: 2944.76 (Ha); 57.22 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 533767; 45.82 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 5146.79 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.03 (Ha)

Radom

Green quiet areas in Radom urban centre

Radom (PL) , Inhabitants 2021: 168072
Total green area (Ha) 197.86
Total green quiet area: 87.81 (Ha); 44.38 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 38583; 20.14 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 197.86 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.27 (Ha)

Regensburg

Green quiet areas in Regensburg urban centre

Regensburg (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 145411
Total green area (Ha) 368.22
Total green quiet area: 150.34 (Ha); 40.83 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 54010; 38.89 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 391.4 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 23.18 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.76 (Ha)

Reims

Green quiet areas in Reims urban centre

Reims (FR) , Inhabitants 2021: 202243
Total green area (Ha) 318.37
Total green quiet area: 80.44 (Ha); 25.27 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 66783; 32.07 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 318.37 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 0.62 (Ha)

Rennes

Green quiet areas in Rennes urban centre

Rennes (FR) , Inhabitants 2021: 231106
Total green area (Ha) 312.17
Total green quiet area: 184.7 (Ha); 59.17 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 82846; 36.6 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 312.17 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.61 (Ha)

Reutlingen

Green quiet areas in Reutlingen urban centre

Reutlingen (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 108335
Total green area (Ha) 163.28
Total green quiet area: 91.39 (Ha); 55.97 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 19884; 20.93 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 189.11 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 25.83 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.07 (Ha)

Rīga

Green quiet areas in Rīga urban centre

0 5 km

Non quiet green and forest	
Urban centre	

Rīga (LV) , Inhabitants 2021: 512437

Total green area (Ha) 1669.99

Total green quiet area: 1007.91 (Ha); 60.35 (%)

People with acces to green quiet area 223320; 42.24 (%)

Green area in Urban centre 1684.92 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 14.93 (Ha)

Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 4.64 (Ha)

Rijeka

Green quiet areas in Rijeka urban centre

Rijeka (HR) , Inhabitants 2021: 101893
Total green area (Ha) 426.27
Total green quiet area: 245.28 (Ha); 57.54 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 46549; 42.15 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 453.2 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 26.93 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.07 (Ha)

Rostock

Green quiet areas in Rostock urban centre

Rostock (), Inhabitants 2021: 128129

Total green area (Ha) 275.18

Total green quiet area: 183.65 (Ha); 66.74 (%)

People with acces to green quiet area 26465; 23.04 (%)

Green area in Urban centre 275.4 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0.22 (Ha)

Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.46 (Ha)

Rotterdam

Green quiet areas in Rotterdam urban centre

Rotterdam (NL) , Inhabitants 2021: 905898
Total green area (Ha) 1665.95
Total green quiet area: 846.87 (Ha); 50.83 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 394969; 46.51 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 1966.25 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 300.3 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.53 (Ha)

Rouen

Green quiet areas in Rouen urban centre

Rouen (FR) , Inhabitants 2021: 306401
Total green area (Ha) 909.6
Total green quiet area: 401.49 (Ha); 44.14 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 55392; 17.91 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 909.6 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.47 (Ha)

Ruhrgebiet

Green quiet areas in Ruhrgebiet urban centre

0 5 10 km

Ruhrgebiet (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 2836083

Total green area (Ha) 13153.95

Total green quiet area: 7009.57 (Ha); 53.29 (%)

People with acces to green quiet area 756027; 29.5 (%)

Green area in Urban centre 15976.28 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 2822.33 (Ha)

Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 4.5 (Ha)

Rzeszów

Green quiet areas in Rzeszów urban centre

GUGIK, Esri, TomTom, Garmin, Foursquare, GeoTechnologies, Inc, METI/NASA, USGS

Rzeszów (PL) , Inhabitants 2021: 142859

Total green area (Ha) 201.35

Total green quiet area: 103.07 (Ha); 51.19 (%)

People with acces to green quiet area 29770; 18.12 (%)

Green area in Urban centre 201.35 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)

Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.28 (Ha)

Saarbrücken

Green quiet areas in Saarbrücken urban centre

Saarbrücken (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 113980
Total green area (Ha) 1001.86
Total green quiet area: 614.76 (Ha); 61.36 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 42199; 36.22 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 1001.86 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.07 (Ha)

Saint-Etienne

Green quiet areas in Saint-Etienne urban centre

Saint-Etienne (FR) , Inhabitants 2021: 177825
Total green area (Ha) 439.11
Total green quiet area: 302.24 (Ha); 68.83 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 65205; 36.03 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 439.11 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.5 (Ha)

Saint-Priest / Mions

Green quiet areas in Saint-Priest / Mions urban centre

- Light green: Quiet green
- Dark green: Quiet forests
- Red: Non quiet green and forest
- Black outline: Urban centre

Saint-Priest / Mions (FR) , Inhabitants 2021: 52455
Total green area (Ha) 25.59
Total green quiet area: 16.65 (Ha); 65.06 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 10987; 21.71 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 25.59 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.21 (Ha)

Salzburg

Green quiet areas in Salzburg urban centre

Salzburg (AT) , Inhabitants 2021: 143281
Total green area (Ha) 418.56
Total green quiet area: 258.08 (Ha); 61.66 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 49855; 36.03 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 439.95 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 21.39 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.04 (Ha)

Sebastián/Donostia

Green quiet areas in San Sebastián/Donostia urban centre

0 5 km

Non quiet green and forest	
Urban centre	

San Sebastián/Donostia (ES) , Inhabitants 2021: 238892
Total green area (Ha) 158.6
Total green quiet area: 46.55 (Ha); 29.35 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 56538; 32.72 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 533.42 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 374.82 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 0.65 (Ha)

Scharwoude / Heerhugowaard

Green quiet areas in Scharwoude / Heerhugowaard urban centre

Scharwoude / Heerhugowaard (NL) , Inhabitants 2021: 68565
Total green area (Ha) 283.68
Total green quiet area: 174.15 (Ha); 61.39 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 38412; 54.38 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 283.68 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.35 (Ha)

Solingen

Green quiet areas in Solingen urban centre

Solingen (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 235527
Total green area (Ha) 1003.63
Total green quiet area: 548.81 (Ha); 54.68 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 50499; 34.12 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 1481.05 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 477.42 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 4.44 (Ha)

Spijkensisse

Green quiet areas in Spijkensisse urban centre

Spijkensisse (NL) , Inhabitants 2021: 121671
Total green area (Ha) 384.9
Total green quiet area: 245.96 (Ha); 63.9 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 65905; 53.73 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 384.9 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.67 (Ha)

Split

Green quiet areas in Split urban centre

Split (HR) , Inhabitants 2021: 163766
Total green area (Ha) 152.41
Total green quiet area: 92.77 (Ha); 60.87 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 17503; 11.47 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 192.37 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 39.96 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 6.68 (Ha)

St. Gallen

Green quiet areas in St. Gallen urban centre

St. Gallen (CH) , Inhabitants 2021: 73882
Total green area (Ha) 465.16
Total green quiet area: 387.88 (Ha); 83.39 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 31801; 40.42 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 465.16 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 8.07 (Ha)

Stavanger

Green quiet areas in Stavanger urban centre

0 5 km

- | | |
|---|--|
| Non quiet green and forest |
| Urban centre |

Stavanger (NO) , Inhabitants 2021: 196314
Total green area (Ha) 565.67
Total green quiet area: 420.6 (Ha); 74.35 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 89669; 53.47 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 598.39 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 32.72 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.44 (Ha)

Stockholm

Green quiet areas in Stockholm urban centre

Stockholm (SE) , Inhabitants 2021: 1462910
Total green area (Ha) 5446.7
Total green quiet area: 3186.5 (Ha); 58.5 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 707237; 64.43 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 8327.01 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 2880.31 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 4.24 (Ha)

Stuttgart

Green quiet areas in Stuttgart urban centre

Stuttgart (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 634685
Total green area (Ha) 2357.56
Total green quiet area: 1624.15 (Ha); 68.89 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 221271; 46.16 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 2664.56 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 307 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 9.75 (Ha)

Szczecin

Green quiet areas in Szczecin urban centre

Szczecin (PL) , Inhabitants 2021: 283281

Total green area (Ha) 638.18

Total green quiet area; 383.97 (Ha); 60.17 (%)

People with acces to green quiet area 53517; 18.11 (%)

Green area in Urban centre 638.19 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0.01 (Ha)

Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.25 (Ha)

Tallin

Green quiet areas in Tallinn urban centre

Tallinn (EE) , Inhabitants 2021: 398161
Total green area (Ha) 1513.32
Total green quiet area: 1226.97 (Ha); 81.08 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 178886; 45.32 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 1518.81 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 5.49 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 4.85 (Ha)

Tampere / Tammerfors

Green quiet areas in Tampere / Tammerfors urban centre

- | | |
|---|--|
| Non quiet green and forest |
| Urban centre |

Tampere / Tammerfors (FI) , Inhabitants 2021: 192372
Total green area (Ha) 1796.15
Total green quiet area: 1016.24 (Ha); 56.58 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 89868; 45.89 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 1801.4 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 5.25 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.37 (Ha)

Tarnów

Green quiet areas in Tarnów urban centre

- Light green: Quiet green
- Dark green: Quiet forests
- Red: Non quiet green and forest
- Black outline: Urban centre

Tarnów (PL) , Inhabitants 2021: 71623
Total green area (Ha) 115.17
Total green quiet area: 82.38 (Ha); 71.53 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 12124; 14.43 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 115.17 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.07 (Ha)

Tartu

Green quiet areas in Tartu urban centre

Tartu (EE) , Inhabitants 2021: 84168
Total green area (Ha) 192
Total green quiet area; 136.55 (Ha); 71.12 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 35586; 42.21 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 193.55 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 1.55 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.24 (Ha)

Torrejón de Ardoz

Green quiet areas in Torrejón de Ardoz urban centre

Torrejón de Ardoz (ES) , Inhabitants 2021: 130757
Total green area (Ha) 103.28
Total green quiet area: 29.14 (Ha); 28.21 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 53771; 42.22 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 111.85 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 8.57 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 0.64 (Ha)

Torun

Green quiet areas in Toruń urban centre

Toruń (PL) , Inhabitants 2021: 157617
Total green area (Ha) 744.45
Total green quiet area; 495.59 (Ha); 66.57 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 67426; 38.4 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 744.45 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.44 (Ha)

Tours

Green quiet areas in Tours urban centre

Tours (FR) , Inhabitants 2021: 222064
Total green area (Ha) 660.94
Total green quiet area: 428.82 (Ha); 64.88 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 92396; 41.51 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 660.94 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.45 (Ha)

Trondheim

Green quiet areas in Trondheim urban centre

Trondheim (NO) , Inhabitants 2021: 185703
Total green area (Ha) 1289.85
Total green quiet area: 954.85 (Ha); 74.03 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 79888; 45.1 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 1307.75 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 17.9 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 6.68 (Ha)

Turku / Åbo

Green quiet areas in Turku / Åbo urban centre

Turku / Åbo (FI) , Inhabitants 2021: 177326
Total green area (Ha) 1494.97
Total green quiet area: 1059.81 (Ha); 70.89 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 64989; 39.31 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 1769.88 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 274.91 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 7.92 (Ha)

Tychy

Green quiet areas in Tychy urban centre

Tychy (PL) , Inhabitants 2021: 106888

Total green area (Ha) 233.16

Total green quiet area: 148.4 (Ha); 63.65 (%)

People with acces to green quiet area 39458; 34.82 (%)

Green area in Urban centre 253.77 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 20.61 (Ha)

Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.2 (Ha)

Ulm/Neu-Ulm

Green quiet areas in Ulm/Neu-Ulm urban centre

Ulm/Neu-Ulm (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 135182
Total green area (Ha) 344.82
Total green quiet area: 204.33 (Ha); 59.26 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 38207; 43.87 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 476.14 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 131.32 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.25 (Ha)

Umeå

Green quiet areas in Umeå urban centre

Umeå (SE) , Inhabitants 2021: 84347
Total green area (Ha) 949.3
Total green quiet area: 421.74 (Ha); 44.43 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 27183; 31.82 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 949.3 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 7.67 (Ha)

Uppsala

Green quiet areas in Uppsala urban centre

Uppsala (SE) , Inhabitants 2021: 158784
Total green area (Ha) 863.34
Total green quiet area: 620.67 (Ha); 71.89 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 102879; 67.12 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 863.34 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 4.07 (Ha)

Ústí and Labem

Green quiet areas in Ústí nad Labem urban centre

Ústí nad Labem (CZ) , Inhabitants 2021: 56675
Total green area (Ha) 355.02
Total green quiet area: 292.43 (Ha); 82.37 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 27146; 44.43 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 364.67 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 9.65 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 7.64 (Ha)

Utrecht

Green quiet areas in Utrecht urban centre

Utrecht (NL) , Inhabitants 2021: 346992
Total green area (Ha) 557.2
Total green quiet area: 240.73 (Ha); 43.2 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 138598; 40.57 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 566.74 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 9.54 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.86 (Ha)

Vaihingen / Möhringen

Green quiet areas in Vaihingen / Möhringen urban centre

- | | |
|---|--|
| Non quiet green and forest |
| Urban centre |

Vaihingen / Möhringen (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 77863
Total green area (Ha) 296.59
Total green quiet area: 161.37 (Ha); 54.41 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 37169; 46.91 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 296.59 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.51 (Ha)

Valencia

Green quiet areas in Valencia urban centre

Valencia (ES) , Inhabitants 2021: 1386286
Total green area (Ha) 407.89
Total green quiet area; 35.77 (Ha); 8.77 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 241773; 30.99 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 708.36 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 300.47 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 0.35 (Ha)

Valladolid

Green quiet areas in Valladolid urban centre

Valladolid (ES) , Inhabitants 2021: 302345
Total green area (Ha) 409.08
Total green quiet area: 189.65 (Ha); 46.36 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 132600; 45.74 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 482.52 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 73.44 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.19 (Ha)

Valletta

Green quiet areas in Valletta urban centre

Valletta (MT) , Inhabitants 2021: 344098
Total green area (Ha) 109.46
Total green quiet area: 41.37 (Ha); 37.79 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 67842; 21.98 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 111.15 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 1.69 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 0.16 (Ha)

Västerås

Green quiet areas in Västerås urban centre

- | | |
|---|--|
| Non quiet green and forest |
| Urban centre |

Västerås (SE) , Inhabitants 2021: 113479
Total green area (Ha) 757.2
Total green quiet area: 370.9 (Ha); 48.98 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 44273; 38.06 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 757.2 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 6.55 (Ha)

Vigo

Green quiet areas in Vigo urban centre

Vigo (ES) , Inhabitants 2021: 251740
Total green area (Ha) 254.49
Total green quiet area: 119.34 (Ha); 46.89 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 100543; 40.5 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 255.72 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 1.23 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.1 (Ha)

Vitoria/Gasteiz

Green quiet areas in Vitoria/Gasteiz urban centre

Vitoria/Gasteiz (ES) , Inhabitants 2021: 242941
Total green area (Ha) 262.5
Total green quiet area: 62.48 (Ha); 23.8 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 130343; 56.37 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 359.15 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 96.65 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 0.88 (Ha)

Warszawa

Green quiet areas in Warszawa urban centre

Warszawa (PL) , Inhabitants 2021: 1821747
Total green area (Ha) 4195.56
Total green quiet area: 1663.51 (Ha); 39.65 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 401153; 25.05 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 4766.06 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 570.5 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 4.45 (Ha)

Wien

Green quiet areas in Wien urban centre

Wien (AT) , Inhabitants 2021: 1890603
Total green area (Ha) 3492.85
Total green quiet area: 2106.55 (Ha); 60.31 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 871281; 46.53 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 3492.85 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.76 (Ha)

Wiesbaden

Green quiet areas in Wiesbaden urban centre

Wiesbaden (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 198154
Total green area (Ha) 340.72
Total green quiet area: 144.93 (Ha); 42.54 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 39675; 19.62 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 340.72 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.16 (Ha)

Winterthur

Green quiet areas in Winterthur urban centre

Winterthur (CH), Inhabitants 2021: 108030
Total green area (Ha) 673.4
Total green quiet area: 478.14 (Ha); 71 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 41697; 38.89 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 673.4 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 9.5 (Ha)

Włocławek

Green quiet areas in Włocławek urban centre

Włocławek (PL) , Inhabitants 2021: 84786
Total green area (Ha) 383.76
Total green quiet area: 265.07 (Ha); 69.07 (%)
People with access to green quiet area 22109; 22.96 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 407.19 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 23.43 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.97 (Ha)

Wroclaw

Green quiet areas in Wroclaw urban centre

Wroclaw (PL) , Inhabitants 2021: 573339
Total green area (Ha) 1205.74
Total green quiet area: 669.97 (Ha); 55.57 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 101020; 18.25 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 1211.1 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 5.36 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.67 (Ha)

Wuppertal

Green quiet areas in Wuppertal urban centre

0 5 km

Non quiet green and forest	
Urban centre	

Wuppertal (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 282077

Total green area (Ha) 1145.26

Total green quiet area: 704.37 (Ha); 61.5 (%)

People with acces to green quiet area 81933; 28.58 (%)

Green area in Urban centre 1146.42 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 1.16 (Ha)

Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 5.95 (Ha)

Würzburg

Green quiet areas in Würzburg urban centre

Würzburg (DE) , Inhabitants 2021: 109793
Total green area (Ha) 463.21
Total green quiet area: 242.46 (Ha); 52.34 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 41007; 37.12 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 610.33 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 147.12 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.84 (Ha)

Zagreb

Green quiet areas in Zagreb urban centre

0 5 km

Non quiet green and forest	
Urban centre	

Zagreb (HR) , Inhabitants 2021: 622154
Total green area (Ha) 1550.7
Total green quiet area: 981.11 (Ha); 63.27 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 162080; 24.25 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 1550.7 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 3.84 (Ha)

Zielona Góra

Green quiet areas in Zielona Góra urban centre

Zielona Góra (PL) , Inhabitants 2021: 92503
Total green area (Ha) 346.34
Total green quiet area: 262.46 (Ha); 75.78 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 41697; 29.55 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 346.34 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 4.04 (Ha)

Zoetermeer

Green quiet areas in Zoetermeer urban centre

Zoetermeer (NL) , Inhabitants 2021: 126495
Total green area (Ha) 360.79
Total green quiet area: 136.81 (Ha); 37.92 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 70558; 57.35 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 360.79 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 1.34 (Ha)

Zürich

Green quiet areas in Zürich urban centre

Zürich (CH) , Inhabitants 2021: 741667
Total green area (Ha) 4346.69
Total green quiet area: 3179.27 (Ha); 73.14 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 240061; 32.69 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 4346.76 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0.07 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 18.23 (Ha)

Zwolle

Green quiet areas in Zwolle urban centre

Zwolle (NL) , Inhabitants 2021: 116637
Total green area (Ha) 460.63
Total green quiet area: 325.53 (Ha); 70.67 (%)
People with acces to green quiet area 93806; 81.5 (%)
Green area in Urban centre 460.63 (Ha); Outside noise maps ; 0 (Ha)
Weighted median of quiet green urban areas; 2.16 (Ha)

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